

1 Algal-derived extracts act as selective ecological filters shaping soil 2 microbiomes, bacterial traits, and tomato performance under biotic stress

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15 **Abstract:**

16 Modern agriculture faces the dual challenge of increasing food production while reducing reliance on synthetic
17 inputs that degrade soil ecosystems and compromise long-term sustainability. Algal biomasses have emerged
18 as promising biostimulants, yet their capacity to selectively modulate soil microbiomes and plant growth-
19 promoting bacterial (PGPB) functions remains poorly understood. Here, we evaluated 17 phylogenetically and
20 biochemically diverse macro- and microalgal extracts to determine their effects on soil microbial communities,
21 bacterial functional traits, and tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) performance. Algal supplementation selectively
22 restructured microbial communities without disrupting overall diversity, promoting taxa associated with plant-
23 beneficial functions, including *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, and Actinobacteria. In soil microcosms, specific
24 treatments increased culturable bacterial abundance by up to ~200-fold relative to the initial soil. Functional
25 assays revealed strong extract- and strain-dependent responses. Siderophore production and ACC-
26 associated activity were the most consistently stimulated traits, whereas auxin production, biofilm formation,
27 and proline synthesis showed more variable or context-dependent responses. Notably, *Ulva* sp. (AP11.2)
28 enhanced siderophore production across the majority of isolates, with over four-fold increases in individual
29 strains, while *Arthrospira*-derived extracts (NG4.1, N14.1) consistently promoted bacterial growth across
30 multiple taxa. In contrast, extracts such as *Nannochloropsis* sp. (NG6.1) and *Tetraselmis* sp. (NG5.1) induced
31 more selective or inhibitory responses, highlighting extract-dependent functional trade-offs. Integration of
32 biochemical and biological datasets identified fatty acid composition as a key axis associated with microbial
33 functional responses, whereas volatile organic compound profiles showed weaker and less consistent
34 associations. These microbiome and functional shifts translated into improved plant performance, with algal
35 treatments increasing tomato growth and reducing mortality by approximately 20% under non-sterile soil
36 conditions characterized by pathogen-associated pressure. Together, these findings demonstrate that algal
37 extracts act as selective modulators of soil microbiomes, enhancing specific bacterial functions and improving
38 plant performance in a context-dependent manner. This work provides a mechanistic framework for the
39 development of targeted algal-based biostimulants aimed at reducing agrochemical inputs and advancing
40 microbiome-informed agriculture.

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42 **Keywords:** soil microbiome, algal extracts, biostimulants, plant growth-promoting bacteria (PGPB), *Solanum*
43 *lycopersicum* microbiota, biostimulants, microbial functions

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45 1 INTRODUCTION

46 Soil degradation and the increasing demand for agricultural productivity are placing unprecedented pressure
47 on global food systems. Current estimates indicate that nearly 40% of the global land surface is degraded,
48 affecting over 3.2 billion people worldwide (Talukder et al., 2021; Vicente-Serrano et al., 2024). At the same
49 time, agricultural production must increase by up to 70% by 2050 to meet rising food demand (Wijerathna-
50 Yapa and Pathirana, 2022). Addressing this challenge requires a transition from input-intensive systems
51 towards more sustainable approaches that harness biological processes rather than relying solely on synthetic
52 inputs, which have contributed to soil degradation, biodiversity loss, and disruption of soil microbial
53 communities (Ogidi and Akpan, 2023; D’Odorico et al., 2019). In this context, the soil microbiome has emerged
54 as a central regulator of plant performance, influencing nutrient cycling, plant growth, and resilience to
55 environmental stress. Rather than passive components of the soil environment, microbial communities actively
56 shape plant outcomes through complex functional interactions, including phytohormone production, nutrient
57 mobilization, and stress mitigation (Dellagnezze and Sierra-Garcia, 2023). Consequently, strategies that
58 modulate microbiome composition and function represent a promising avenue for improving crop productivity
59 in a sustainable manner.

60 Biostimulants have gained increasing attention as tools to enhance plant growth and resilience through
61 biological mechanisms. These include a wide range of substances and microorganisms that act directly on
62 plant physiology or indirectly through interactions with the soil microbiome (Yakhin et al., 2017; Buss et al.,
63 2025). Among these, algal-derived biomasses are particularly promising due to their rich and diverse
64 biochemical composition, including phytohormones, polysaccharides, and lipids. Macroalgae have a long
65 history of agricultural use, while microalgae are increasingly recognized for their capacity to influence soil
66 microbial diversity and function (Wang et al., 2021; Ferreira et al., 2024; Osorio-Reyes et al., 2023). Although
67 algal extracts have been shown to enhance plant growth and modify microbial communities (Wang et al., 2018;
68 Renaut et al., 2019), the mechanisms underlying these effects remain poorly understood. In particular, the
69 links between algal biochemical composition, microbial community restructuring, and the modulation of specific
70 plant growth-promoting bacterial (PGPB) traits are not well resolved. Most studies have examined plant
71 responses or broad shifts in microbial composition in isolation, with limited integration of chemical, microbial,
72 and plant-level data.

73 Addressing this gap requires a more integrated understanding of how algal-derived compounds influence
74 microbial functional traits that directly impact plant performance. Plant growth-promoting bacteria contribute to
75 nutrient acquisition, phytohormone production, and stress tolerance, yet their activity is highly context-
76 dependent and influenced by environmental inputs. Identifying which biochemical features of algal biomasses
77 drive these functional responses is therefore critical for the rational design of microbiome-based biostimulants.
78 We hypothesized that algal extracts act as selective ecological filters that drive deterministic shifts in soil
79 microbial communities, leading to trait-specific modulation of plant growth-promoting bacterial functions.
80 Furthermore, we hypothesized that these effects are linked to specific biochemical features of algal biomasses,
81 particularly fatty acid composition, which may influence microbial physiology and functional outcomes.

82 In this study, we evaluated 17 phylogenetically and biochemically diverse algal biomasses for their capacity to
83 modulate soil microbiomes, influence plant growth-promoting bacterial functions, and enhance tomato
84 (*Solanum lycopersicum*) performance. By integrating algal chemical profiling with microbial community
85 analyses, functional trait assays, and in vivo plant experiments, this work provides a mechanistic framework
86 for understanding algae-mediated microbiome modulation and supports the development of targeted,
87 microbiome-oriented strategies for sustainable agriculture.

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90 **2 MATERIALS AND METHODS**91 **2.1 Algal biomass selection and extract preparation**

92 A total of sixteen dried and powdered algal biomass samples, comprising both microalgae and macroalgae,
 93 were supplied by the microalgal company Necton (Algarve, Portugal). In addition, one commercial biofertilizer
 94 product (Terralgae; Terraguar, Aveiro, Portugal), formulated from multiple algal species, was included in the
 95 study. The algal genus, corresponding sample codes, and application concentrations used in plant tests, soil
 96 microcosms, and bacterial assays are listed in Table 1.

97 Table 1 - Algae biomass samples with their corresponding code names, as well as concentrations for plant
 98 tests and microcosms (g/L) and bacterial assays (% of 10 g/L stock).

Sample Code	Algal Species / Product Name	Plant Test and Microcosm Concentration (g/L)	Bacterial Assay Concentration (% of 10 g/L stock)
NG6.1	<i>Nannochloropsis</i> sp.	3	3
NG7.1	Terralgae - commercial product	3	3
NG8.1	<i>Chlorococcum</i> sp.	3	3
N14.1	<i>Arthrospira platensis</i>	3	3
N15.1	<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i> (premium)	3	3
N33.1	<i>Chaetoceros calcitrans</i>	3	3
N16.2	<i>Tisochrysis lutea</i>	1.5	1.5
N13.3	<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	1.5	1.5
NG1.1	<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i> (honey)	1.5	1.5
IA9.1	<i>Gelidium</i> sp.	3	3
AP10.2	<i>Fucus vesiculosus</i>	3	3
NG2.1	<i>Tetraselmis</i> sp.	3	3
NG3.1	<i>Tetradesmus obliquus</i>	1.5	1.5
NG4.1	<i>Arthrospira platensis</i> (organic)	1.5	1.5
NG5.1	<i>Tetraselmis chuii</i>	3	3
N13.2	<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	1.5	1.5
AP11.2	<i>Ulva rigida</i>	0.5	0.5

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100 For extract preparation, dried algal powders were suspended in double-distilled water (ddH₂O) at a
 101 concentration of 10 g/L. Suspensions were incubated under agitation (170 rpm) at 23 °C for 16–20 h to obtain
 102 aqueous extracts. Following extraction, suspensions were filtered through cloth to remove large particulate
 103 material and subsequently diluted with ddH₂O to the concentrations required for plant experiments, soil
 104 microcosms, and bacterial assays. These concentrations were selected based on previous optimization plant
 105 trials conducted by our collaborators. For bacterial assays requiring sterile conditions, extracts were filtered
 106 through 0.22 µm membrane filters prior to use.

107 **2.2. Chemical characterization of algal biomasses**108 **2.2.1 Volatile organic compound analysis (HS-SPME/GC–MS)**

109 Headspace volatile organic compounds (VOCs) were analyzed using solid-phase microextraction coupled to
 110 gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (HS-SPME/GC–MS). A manual SPME fibre coated with
 111 polydimethylsiloxane/divinylbenzene (PDMS/DVB, 65 µm; Supelco, Bellefonte, PA, USA) was used and

112 conditioned according to the manufacturer's instructions. For each analysis, 0.5 g of algal biomass was placed
113 in a 20 mL glass vial, to which 2 mL of deionized water and 0.5 g NaCl were added to promote volatilization.
114 Vials were sealed with PTFE/silicone septa and incubated in a PAL 120 RSI autosampler equipped with a
115 heating compartment. Samples were equilibrated at 40 °C for 15 min, followed by headspace extraction for 45
116 min. Following extraction, the SPME fibre was retracted, transferred to the GC injector, and thermally desorbed
117 at 250 °C for 7 min. Analyses were performed using an Agilent 7890B gas chromatograph coupled to an
118 Agilent 5977A mass spectrometer (Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, CA, USA), equipped with an HP-5MS
119 capillary column (30 m × 0.25 mm, 0.25 µm). The injector operated at 250 °C in split mode (1:5), with helium
120 as the carrier gas at a constant flow rate of 1.0 mL min⁻¹. The oven temperature program started at 70 °C (2
121 min), ramped at 3 °C min⁻¹ to 200 °C, and was held at 200 °C for 18 min. The mass spectrometer operated in
122 electron ionization mode (70 eV), scanning m/z 40–400. Injector and detector temperatures were set to 250 °C
123 and 300 °C, respectively. Compound identification was based on comparison with Wiley 9 and NIST 17 mass
124 spectral libraries, as well as retention indices calculated using C9–C25 n-alkanes. Each sample was analyzed
125 in triplicate, and results are reported as mean values.

126 **2.2.2 Fatty acid analysis (GC–FID)**

127 Total lipids were extracted using the Folch method with chloroform/methanol (2:1, v/v) (Folch et al., 1957).
128 Preparation of fatty acid methyl esters (FAMES) followed the methodology described in Jerković et al. (2021).
129 FAMES were analyzed using a Shimadzu GC-2010 Plus gas chromatograph equipped with a flame ionization
130 detector (FID) and an SH-FAMEWAX™ capillary column (30 m × 0.32 mm i.d., 0.25 µm film thickness). The
131 injector and detector temperatures were set to 240 °C and 250 °C, respectively. A 2 µL injection volume was
132 used with a split ratio of 1:100. The oven temperature program was as follows: initial temperature 120 °C (held
133 for 5 min), increased to 220 °C at 5 °C min⁻¹, and held for 20 min. Nitrogen was used as the carrier gas at a
134 constant flow rate of 1.26 mL min⁻¹. Fatty acids were identified by comparison with a certified reference
135 standard (Supelco F.A.M.E. Mix, C4–C24), analyzed under identical conditions. Results were expressed as
136 the percentage of each fatty acid relative to total fatty acids.

137 **2.3 Soil microcosm and culturable microbial analysis**

138 Topsoil (0–15 cm) was collected from six tomato field sites in Vila Franca de Xira, Portugal (pathogen
139 proliferation reported soil). Samples were sieved to remove debris and combined in equal volumes to produce
140 a homogenized soil mixture representative of the initial microbial community. Baseline culturable bacterial
141 abundance was estimated by suspending approximately 0.5 mL of mixed soil in 0.45% NaCl solution, followed
142 by serial dilution (10⁻¹-10⁻⁴) and plating on LB agar. Plates were incubated at 28 °C for 24 h, after which
143 colony-forming units (CFUs) were enumerated and normalized to dry soil weight. Morphologically distinct
144 colonies were isolated and purified for further analysis. Microcosms were established by adding 4 mL of each
145 algal extract (Table 1), water, or NPK fertilizer (3.825 mL/L) to 25 mL of homogenized soil in 50 mL conical
146 tubes. Samples were thoroughly mixed and incubated for 7 days at room temperature.

147 Following incubation, culturable bacteria were re-isolated using the same serial dilution and plating approach.
148 Changes in CFU abundance and relative composition were assessed relative to the initial soil. Morphologically
149 distinct colonies exhibiting a relative abundance increase greater than 5% were selected for taxonomic
150 identification. Genomic DNA was extracted using a heat-shock method (95 °C for 10 min), and the V5-V8
151 region of the bacterial 16S rRNA gene was amplified using primers 799F and 1392R. PCR products were
152 verified by agarose gel electrophoresis and sequenced by Sanger sequencing (GENEWIZ, Germany).
153 Taxonomic assignment was performed using BLAST against the NCBI database.

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157 **2.4 Metabarcoding analysis**

158 **2.4.1 DNA extraction and sequencing**

159 Metabarcoding analyses were performed on samples of the initial soil (T0) and soils collected from each
160 microcosm after 7 days of incubation (T1). Samples were stored at $-70\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ prior to DNA extraction. Total DNA
161 was extracted using the DNeasy PowerSoil Pro Kit (Qiagen, Netherlands) according to the manufacturer's
162 instructions. DNA quantity and quality were assessed using a NanoDrop One/One^c microvolume
163 spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific, USA). Bacterial community composition was characterized by
164 amplifying the V3-V4 region of the 16S rRNA gene using primers 341F and 806R. PCR amplification consisted
165 of an initial denaturation at $95\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 3 min, followed by 25 cycles of denaturation ($95\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, 30 s), annealing
166 ($55\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, 30 s), and extension ($72\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, 45 s), with a final extension at $72\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 10 min. Purified amplicons were
167 pooled in equimolar concentrations and sequenced on an Illumina NovaSeq platform (2×250 bp paired-end)
168 by Novogene (Cambridge, UK).

169 **2.4.2 Bioinformatic processing**

170 Sequencing data were processed using QIIME2 (v2020.6). Quality filtering, denoising, chimera removal, and
171 paired-end merging were performed using the DADA2 plugin. Based on quality profiles, forward and reverse
172 reads were truncated at 280 bp and 210 bp, respectively. Amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) were inferred
173 and retained for downstream analyses. Taxonomic classification was performed using a Naive Bayes classifier
174 trained on the SILVA 138 reference database, trimmed to the V3-V4 region. Singleton and extremely low-
175 abundance ASVs were removed prior to analysis.

176 **2.4.3 Community composition, diversity, and functional prediction**

177 ASV tables were collapsed to class, family, genus, and species levels, and relative abundances were
178 calculated per sample. Alpha diversity metrics (Chao1 richness, Shannon diversity, Simpson diversity,
179 dominance, and Pielou's evenness) were computed using QIIME2 and R (vegan package). Differences among
180 treatments were assessed using ANOVA followed by Tukey's HSD test. Beta diversity was evaluated using
181 weighted UniFrac distances. Ordination analyses included PCoA, PCA, NMDS, and DCA, and hierarchical
182 clustering was performed using UPGMA. Treatment effects were tested using PERMANOVA. Microbial
183 functional potential was inferred using PICRUSt2, with predicted functions annotated against KEGG Orthology,
184 KEGG pathways (Levels 1-3), enzyme commission numbers, COG, Pfam, and TIGRFAM databases.
185 Community assembly processes were assessed using β NTI, phylogenetic normalized stochasticity ratio
186 (ρ NST), and iCAMP.

187 **2.5 Plant growth-promoting bacterial trait assays**

188 Bacterial isolates were evaluated for plant growth-promoting traits including growth rate, biofilm formation,
189 auxin production, ACC deaminase activity, proline production, and siderophore production using microplate-
190 based assays. Strains were pre-cultured in LB broth (Miller's modification, 20 g/L) at $28\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ under agitation
191 (180 rpm) for 12–16 h. Cultures were standardized to an OD600 of 0.05 and distributed into 96-well plates
192 with a final volume of 200 μL per well, consisting of bacterial culture, algal extract (Table X), and assay-specific
193 components. Each assay included treatment, culture-only control, and extract-only control, and all conditions
194 were performed in triplicate. Biofilm formation was quantified using a crystal violet assay (Coffey and
195 Anderson, 2014). Auxin production was assessed using a modified Salkowski assay (Gang et al., 2019). ACC
196 deaminase activity was inferred from growth in M9 medium supplemented with ACC as the sole carbon source
197 (Naveed et al., 2008). Proline production was measured using a ninhydrin-based assay (Goswami et al.,

198 2022), and siderophore production was quantified using the chrome azurol sulfonate (CAS) assay (Arora and
199 Verma, 2017).

200 **2.6 Tomato seedling assay**

201 Three algal biomasses were selected for plant experiments: AP11.2 (*Ulva rigida*), N13.3 (*Skeletonema*
202 *costatum*), and N16.2 (*Tisochrysis lutea*), based on previous screening trials and biochemical assay results.
203 Extracts were applied at concentrations of 0.5, 1.5, and 1.5 g/L, respectively. Soil was collected and prepared
204 as described above and mixed with turf at a ratio of 3:1 (v/v). To distinguish between direct and microbiome-
205 mediated effects, half of the soil was tyndallized by heating at 70 °C for three consecutive days, with
206 intermediate aeration periods to allow germination of resistant propagules. Tomato seeds (*Solanum*
207 *lycopersicum*) were surface sterilized in 70% ethanol for 10 min, rinsed with ddH₂O, and soaked overnight.
208 Seeds were sown directly into 0.25 L pots. Plants were watered daily with 40 mL of water. Algal extracts (40
209 mL) were applied three weeks after sowing, followed by a second application one week later. One week after
210 the second application, plants were harvested, roots were washed, and root and shoot lengths were quantified
211 using ImageJ (v1.54p). A two-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test was used to evaluate the effects
212 of soil type, treatment, and their interaction.

213 **2.7 Statistical and multivariate analyses**

214 Volatile compound and fatty acid datasets were normalized to relative abundances (%) and log-transformed
215 [$\log_{10}(x + 1 \times 10^{-6})$] to stabilize variance. Hierarchical clustering was performed using Euclidean distance and
216 average linkage. Heatmaps were generated using the dendrogram order. Datasets of volatile compounds
217 (VOCs) and fatty acids were arranged as feature-by-sample tables. Values were converted to per-sample
218 relative abundances (%) summing to 100%, then log-transformed as $\log_{10}(x + 1 \times 10^{-6})$ to stabilize variance
219 and retain zeros. This scaling minimized dominance of high-abundance compounds and enabled comparison
220 across samples. Samples were grouped by hierarchical clustering (Euclidean distance, average linkage), and
221 heat maps were generated using the dendrogram order. For VOCs, class-specific panels and a compact map
222 of the 30 most variable compounds (based on log-scale variance) were produced. All visualizations were
223 created in Python (Matplotlib/SciPy). Warmer colors indicate higher relative abundance. Other statistical
224 analyses were performed using GraphPad Prism (v10.6.0). Data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation
225 ($n = 3$), and differences among treatments were assessed using one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's post
226 hoc test ($p < 0.05$). Spearman's rank correlations were calculated to assess relationships between biochemical
227 profiles (VOCs and fatty acids) and bacterial functional traits. Correlations with $|r| \geq 0.5$ were considered
228 biologically relevant.

229 **3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

230 **3.1 Volatile organic compound profiles and sample clustering**

231 Volatile organic compounds (VOCs) were characterized by HS-SPME/GC-MS, revealing a broadly conserved
232 class-level composition across algal biomasses, dominated by terpenoid-derived compounds and ketones
233 (Figure 1; Annex A1). Apocarotenoids and other oxygenated terpenoids accounted for approximately 10-43%
234 of total identified volatiles and frequently represented the most abundant class. These included recurrent
235 carotenoid cleavage products such as β -cyclocitral, safranal, α/β -ionone, 4-oxoisophorone, and
236 dihydroactinidiolide, consistent with oxidative carotenoid metabolism in photosynthetic organisms (Simkin,
237 2021). Ketones constituted the second major class (8-33%), comprising both aliphatic enones (C7-C9) and
238 cyclic ketones. Alcohols represented a smaller fraction (5-8%), with 1-octen-3-ol and hex-1-en-3-ol frequently
239 detected. The presence of 1-octen-3-ol is consistent with linoleic acid oxidation and has been associated with
240 antimicrobial activity in vitro (Xiong et al., 2017).

241 Aldehydes ranged from trace levels to 26% and were dominated by C6–C10 saturated and unsaturated
 242 species (e.g., hexanal, (E)-2-hexenal, nonanal, decanal), products of the LOX/HPL pathway involved in stress
 243 and defense signaling in photosynthetic organisms (Bate and Rothstein, 1998). Carboxylic acids were present
 244 at minor to moderate levels (0–30%), while hydrocarbons were generally low but reached 26–30% in a subset
 245 of samples. Esters and benzenoid derivatives were consistently minor components. Hierarchical clustering
 246 based on VOC class distributions revealed reproducible sample groupings (Figure 1). Several paired or closely
 247 related profiles were observed (e.g., AP10.2-AP11.2; NG5.1-NG6.1; NG3.1-NG8.1; N16.2-N33.1), indicating
 248 broadly similar volatile class patterns within these sets. In contrast, NG1.1 and N14.1 occupied distinct
 249 positions, reflecting divergent class distributions: NG1.1 was characterized by high acids and aldehydes with
 250 minimal hydrocarbons, whereas N14.1 displayed elevated hydrocarbons and alcohols but low aldehydes and
 251 esters. N13.3 was also distinctive, lacking hydrocarbons and showing a ketone-rich profile.

252 Reordering samples according to the dendrogram clarified broader compositional tendencies (Figure 1). A
 253 hydrocarbon-rich group emerged around NG4.1 and N14.1, while NG5.1 and NG6.1 clustered as low-acid
 254 samples enriched in ketones, alcohols, and apocarotenoids. A third group (AP10.2, AP11.2, NG7.1) was
 255 enriched in acids and aldehydes, whereas N16.2 and N33.1 exhibited alcohol- and ketone-rich profiles with
 256 moderate contributions from other classes. Despite these distinctions, most samples shared a conserved
 257 terpenoid–ketone backbone, limiting between-sample contrast at the VOC class level. Although many detected
 258 volatiles have been reported to exhibit biological activity, class-level VOC correlations with bacterial functional
 259 traits were weak and inconsistent. Apart from a recurring negative tendency between ketone abundance and
 260 biofilm formation in some comparisons, no robust or systematic associations were observed. This likely reflects
 261 both the compositional similarity across samples and the complexity of natural volatile mixtures, where
 262 individual compounds may exert opposing or context-dependent effects.

263 Taken together, these results indicate that VOC profiles are relatively conserved across algal biomasses at
 264 the class level, limiting their discriminatory power in explaining treatment-specific microbial and functional
 265 responses. This suggests that, under the conditions tested, VOC composition may play a secondary or
 266 context-dependent role compared to other biochemical fractions.

268 **Figure 1.** Heat-map clustering of VOCs class profiles. (a) Clustered heat-map displaying distribution of VOC
269 classes across 17 algal samples. Values are \log_{10} -transformed relative percentages and are shown on a color
270 scale representing standardized relative abundance (b) Corresponding dendrogram indicating sample
271 similarity based on Euclidean distance.

272 3.2 Fatty acid composition and compositional structuring

273 In contrast to VOCs, fatty acid (FA) profiles exhibited substantially greater compositional variability across
274 algal biomasses (Figure 2; Annex A2). At the class level, saturated fatty acids (SFA) ranged from 24.4 to
275 61.3%, monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFA) from 6.6 to 48.9%, and polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA)
276 showed the widest dispersion, with n-6 PUFA spanning 3.6-40.3% and n-3 PUFA 0.5-51.7%. Thus, the
277 polyunsaturated fraction, particularly n-3 PUFA, represented the principal axis of between-sample variability.

278 At the individual FA level, palmitic acid (C16:0) was consistently abundant and often the dominant component,
279 ranging from approximately 15.5% to 50.0%. The principal MUFA were C16:1 and C18:1 n-9, with the latter
280 varying from trace levels to 38.36%. Within PUFA, some samples were enriched in n-3 species, particularly α -
281 linolenic acid (C18:3 n-3) and eicosapentaenoic acid (C20:5 n-3), whereas others were dominated by n-6 fatty
282 acids such as linoleic acid (C18:2 n-6) and arachidonic acid (C20:4 n-6). Very-long-chain saturated fatty acids
283 (C22:0-C24:0) were present at appreciable levels in only a limited subset of samples.

284 Hierarchical clustering based on the full FA matrix separated samples into three broad compositional
285 tendencies (Figure 2): (i) n-3 PUFA-rich profiles with lower SFA; (ii) n-6-biased profiles with moderate SFA;
286 and (iii) SFA/MUFA-dominated profiles characterized by elevated C16:1 and C18:1 n-9. This structuring
287 provided a clearer and more discriminative chemical framework for interpreting downstream functional
288 responses than VOC class distributions.

289

290 **Figure 2.** Heat-map clustering of fatty acid profiles. (a) Clustered heat-map displaying distribution of fatty acids
291 across 17 algal samples. Values are \log_{10} -transformed relative percentages and are shown on a color scale
292 representing standardized relative abundance (b) Corresponding dendrogram indicating sample similarity
293 based on Euclidean distance.

294 3.3 Taxonomic Responses to Algal Extracts

295 Metabarcoding analysis revealed clear microbial succession in the control microcosm over the incubation
296 period (Figures 3 and 4). The initial soil community (T0) was dominated by Actinobacteria, with Bacilli and
297 Proteobacteria present at lower abundances. Following incubation, the water control (T1) showed a marked
298 shift towards increased relative abundance of Proteobacteria, while Bacilli declined significantly and
299 Actinobacteria remained relatively stable. These trends are consistent with natural soil succession, where
300 Proteobacteria and Actinobacteria outcompete Firmicutes (Fierer et al., 2007). The NPK treatment largely
301 mirrored this trajectory, indicating that chemical fertilization reinforced existing community dynamics rather
302 than inducing substantial compositional shifts. Although minor differences in specific taxa were observed, there
303 was no clear enrichment of classical plant growth-promoting genera. These findings suggest that conventional
304 fertilization maintains dominant microbial groups without substantially enhancing beneficial taxa, highlighting
305 the need for alternative inputs such as algal biostimulants (Geisseler and Scow, 2014; Hartmann et al., 2014).

306 In contrast, algal biostimulants induced distinct and treatment-specific shifts in community composition. For
307 example, extract NG6.1 (*Nannochloropsis* sp.) markedly promoted Actinobacteria, increasing the relative
308 abundance of key genera such as *Streptomyces*, *Nocardioideis*, and *Saccharothrix*, taxa commonly associated
309 with antibiotic production, pathogen suppression, and organic matter turnover (Chater et al., 2016; Ebrahimi-
310 Zarandi et al., 2022). Conversely, N33.1 (*Chaetoceros* sp.) shifted the community towards a Proteobacteria-
311 dominated state, with strong enrichment of *Acinetobacter* and the emergence of *Enterobacter*. N16.2
312 (*Tisochrysis* sp.) also promoted *Enterobacter*, suggesting enrichment of metabolically versatile taxa, although
313 with potential implications for opportunistic behavior depending on environmental context (Bhattacharyya et
314 al., 2017; Alzate Zuluaga et al., 2021). A distinct trajectory was observed for NG4.1 (*Arthrospira* sp.) and
315 NG5.1 (*Tetraselmis* sp.), which restored Bacilli to levels comparable to the initial T0 soil. This shift was driven
316 by increased abundances of *Neobacillus* and *Priestia*, genera frequently associated with plant growth
317 promotion and stress resilience (Mmotla et al., 2025). Similarly, IA9.1 (*Gelidium* sp.) restored Bacilli while
318 additionally promoting *Pseudomonas*, suggesting the potential establishment of synergistic consortia of key
319 plant-beneficial taxa.

320 Notably, several of the enriched genera (e.g., *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, and Actinobacteria) are well-
321 documented producers of siderophores and other plant growth-promoting traits, providing a functional basis
322 for the trait-level responses observed in subsequent assays. Collectively, these findings demonstrate that algal
323 extracts can restructure soil microbial communities through selective enrichment of specific taxonomic groups,
324 either reinforcing functionally relevant guilds or promoting alternative community configurations. While several
325 treatments enhanced taxa linked to plant growth promotion, others favored less conventional groups,
326 underscoring the importance of subsequent functional validation (e.g., biochemical assays) when evaluating
327 their potential as biostimulants.

328
 329
 330 **Figure 3** - Relative abundance of the top 10 bacterial classes in algal microcosm treatments. Clustered
 331 stacked column chart displaying the relative abundances of the ten most dominant bacterial classes in algal
 332 supplemented and control microcosms (colour-coded as shown in the legend), along with a grouped category
 333 for all remaining classes ('others'). 'Initial soil (T0)' represents the original soil community, while all other
 334 treatments, including algal applications and the water and fertilizer (NPK) controls, were assessed after 7 days
 335 (T1).
 336

337
 338
 339 **Figure 4** - Relative abundance of the top 30 bacterial genera in algal microcosm treatments. Clustered stacked
 340 column chart showing the relative abundances of the 30 most abundant bacterial genera in algal supplemented
 341 and control microcosms, along with the combined abundance of the remaining genera grouped as 'others'.
 342 'Initial soil (T0)' represents the original soil community prior to treatment, while all other treatments, including
 343 algal applications and the water and fertilizer (NPK) controls, display the bacterial community after 7 days.
 344 The bacterial genera are color-coded as displayed in the legend.

345 **3.4 Alpha and Beta Diversity**

346 At the community level, alpha diversity metrics indicated that algal supplementation generally preserved
 347 overall community structure (Figure 5). While several extracts were associated with reductions in Shannon
 348 diversity, such as NG6.1 (*Nannochloropsis* sp.), NG7.1 (Terrallgae), and N33.1 (*Chaetoceros* sp.), evenness
 349 remained consistently high across treatments, as reflected in stable Simpson's indices. Conversely, extracts
 350 such as NG2.1 (*Tetraselmis* sp.) and AP10.2 (*Fucus* sp.) were associated with the highest richness and
 351 evenness, respectively, across treatments and controls, suggesting that certain algal extracts may enhance
 352 aspects of microbial diversity.

353 **Figure 5** - Alpha-diversity indices in algal microcosm treatments. Boxplots display the (a) Chao1, (b) Shannon
 354 diversity, (c) Simpson's diversity, and (d) Pielou's evenness indices of the initial soil community (Initial Soil
 355 [T0]) and of communities 7 days after application of aqueous algal extract or water and fertilizer (NPK) as
 356 controls. The lower, middle and upper lines of each box represent the first quartile (25th percentile), median
 357 (50th percentile), and third quartile (75th percentile), respectively, and the whiskers extend to the most extreme
 358 values within 1.5× the interquartile range from the first or third quartile. Statistically significant differences
 359 between treatments are indicated by asterisks (*p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001).
 360
 361

362 Beta diversity analyses further supported overall structural stability. Ordination approaches (including PCA,
 363 PCoA, NMDS, and DCA) showed that the majority of algal-treated communities clustered closely with the
 364 water control at T1, indicating that algal supplementation did not drive large-scale community divergence
 365 (Figure 6). However, NG6.1 (*Nannochloropsis* sp.) and IA9.1 (*Gelidium* sp.) exhibited greater separation in
 366 beta diversity space, consistent with their pronounced taxonomic enrichment patterns. Hence, these findings
 367 indicate that algal extracts can selectively restructure microbial communities while maintaining general
 368 community integrity. This combination of targeted compositional shifts without widespread disruption is a key
 369 property of effective microbial biostimulants.
 370

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 372
 373 **Figure 6** - Beta-diversity DCA analysis of microcosm treatments. Ordination plot from Detrended
 374 Correspondence Analysis (DCA) showing differences in bacterial community composition among 17 algal
 375 supplemented microcosms and water and NPK (fertilizer) controls. Each microcosm includes three replicates
 376 (same-colored circles), with closer points representing more similar communities. DCA1 and DCA2, expressed
 377 as standard deviation units, correspond to the first and second largest gradients of beta diversity.
 378

379 3.5 Functional Potential Shifts

380 Functional predictions using PICRUSt2 provided insight into the potential functional consequences of the
 381 observed community restructuring in response to algal supplementation. At the broadest level (KEGG level 1),
 382 metabolism remained the dominant functional category across all treatments (>80%), indicating that algal
 383 supplementation did not disrupt core microbial functional potential. At finer resolution, extract-specific
 384 functional enrichments were observed. For example, N33.1 (*Chaetoceros* sp.) increased pathways related to
 385 lipid metabolism, xenobiotic degradation, and membrane transport, consistent with the enrichment of
 386 copiotrophic taxa such as *Acinetobacter* and *Enterobacter*.

387 In contrast, NG6.1 (*Nannochloropsis* sp.) enhanced functions associated with secondary metabolite
388 biosynthesis, including ansamycin production, reflecting the increased abundance of Actinobacteria such as
389 *Streptomyces* and *Saccharothrix*. Similarly, NG4.1 and IA9.1 (*Arthrospira* sp.) were associated with
390 enrichment of amino acid metabolism and tricarboxylic acid (TCA) cycle pathways, consistent with the
391 metabolic versatility of Bacilli and *Pseudomonas* enriched under these treatments. Importantly, these
392 functional profiles are inferred from taxonomic composition and therefore represent predicted functional
393 potential rather than direct measurements of microbial activity. As such, while the observed patterns are
394 consistent with the ecological roles of the enriched taxa, they should be interpreted as indicative rather than
395 definitive evidence of functional shifts.

396 Within this context, the alignment between taxonomic enrichment and predicted functional categories suggests
397 that algal extracts modulate microbiome functional potential in ecologically coherent ways. The observed
398 enrichments are consistent with processes relevant to nutrient cycling, stress tolerance, and pathogen
399 suppression. Comparable functional responses have been reported for other organic amendments and
400 biostimulants (Backer et al., 2018; Rouphael and Colla, 2020). However, the treatment-specific and guild-
401 associated patterns observed here highlight the capacity of algal extracts to act as targeted modulators of
402 microbiome functional potential.

403 **3.6 Community Assembly Processes**

404 Null-model analyses revealed that community assembly in algal extract treatments was predominantly
405 governed by deterministic processes (Figure 7). β NTI values were consistently strongly negative, indicating
406 homogeneous selection as the dominant driver of community structuring. In agreement, pNST values
407 remained below the stochasticity threshold of 0.5, further supporting a predominance of deterministic
408 assembly. iCAMP analysis provided a more detailed partitioning of assembly processes, attributing most
409 community turnover to homogeneous selection ($47.6\% \pm 3.0$), with secondary contributions from drift (37.8%
410 ± 3.3) and dispersal limitation ($\sim 12.3\%$). Homogenizing dispersal contributed minimally ($\leq 3\%$), while
411 heterogeneous selection was negligible.

412 Together, these results indicate that algal extracts reinforce the existing soil environmental filter, promoting
413 selective enrichment rather than stochastic community restructuring. The dominance of homogeneous
414 selection suggests that algal-derived inputs impose consistent ecological pressures that favor specific,
415 functionally coherent microbial guilds, such as Actinobacteria or Bacilli. In contrast to untreated or NPK-
416 amended soils, which typically exhibit higher stochasticity, algal-treated systems displayed more constrained
417 and reproducible assembly trajectories. This increased determinism may be advantageous in agronomic
418 contexts, as it implies more predictable enrichment of beneficial microbial groups.

419

420 **Figure 7** - Community Assembly Analysis of Microcosm treatments. β NTI, pNST, and iCAMP analyses across
 421 algal extract, water, and NPK microcosm treatments. (a) Boxplots of β -nearest taxon index (β NTI) for pairwise
 422 comparisons between replicates within each treatment. Values < -2 indicate homogeneous selection, while
 423 values between -2 and $+2$ indicate stochastic assembly. (b) Boxplot of phylogenetic Normalized Stochasticity
 424 Ratio (pNST) for pairwise comparisons between replicates within each treatment. Values < 0.5 indicate
 425 predominantly deterministic assembly, while values > 0.5 indicate predominantly stochastic assembly. (c)
 426 Percent stacked column chart of iCAMP analysis showing the relative contribution of five ecological processes
 427 (homogeneous selection [HoS], heterogeneous selection [HeS], homogenizing dispersal [HD], dispersal
 428 limitation [DL], and drift [DR]) to community assembly within each treatment.

429 **3.7 Population Assay**

430 From the composite soil mix at T0 and the microcosms after 7 days of incubation (T1), a total of 54
 431 morphologically distinct culturable isolates were recovered through plating and morphological characterization.
 432 Relative abundance profiles across treatments revealed clear shifts in culturable community composition
 433 following algal supplementation (Figure 8). Based on an abundance threshold of >5% increase in algal
 434 treatments relative to controls, 16 isolates were selected for taxonomic identification via 16S rRNA gene
 435 sequencing (Table 2). Importantly, the taxonomic identities of the isolated strains broadly aligned with the
 436 dominant or enriched taxa identified through metabarcoding, supporting the representativeness of the
 437 culturable fraction for downstream functional characterization.
 438

439 **Figure 8** - Population distribution of culturable morphologically distinct isolates. Stacked column chart showing
 440 the relative abundances of morphologically distinct culturable isolates (codes indicated in the legend) from
 441 original tomato field soil and in algal-treated microcosms, including water and NPK (universal fertilizer) control
 442 microcosms after seven days.
 443
 444
 445
 446

447 **Table 2** - Identification of morphologically distinct isolates from microcosm analysis. Sixteen selected
 448 morphologically distinct isolates (each with an assigned code name) were identified to species level based on
 449 16S rRNA gene sequences using the BLAST database. The sequence similarity values between each isolate
 450 and the closest database match are also reported.
 451

Strain	Identification	BLAST Threshold (%)
A8	<i>Bacillus sanguinis</i>	99.85
B4	<i>Exiguobacterium acetylicum</i>	98.96
BD	<i>Exiguobacterium acetylicum</i>	99.71
E	<i>Peribacillus frigoritolerans</i>	98.69
F	<i>Enterobacter quasihormaechei</i>	98.85
GW	<i>Priestia aryabhatai</i>	98.97
H	<i>Leclercia adecarboxylata</i>	99.00
K	<i>Enterobacter quasihormaechei</i>	99.70
T	<i>Bacillus australimaris</i>	99.71
V	not identified	
Z	<i>Priestia megaterium</i>	99.11
P	<i>Priestia aryabhatai</i>	99.56
BI	<i>Exiguobacterium acetylicum</i>	99.13
A	not identified	
Q	not identified	
GY	<i>Peribacillus frigoritolerans</i>	99.85

452
 453
 454 All isolates were assigned to genera with well-documented plant growth-promoting bacteria (PGPB), including
 455 *Bacillus*, *Priestia*, *Peribacillus*, *Leclercia*, *Exiguobacterium*, and *Enterobacter*, which are known to exhibit traits
 456 such as phytohormone production, nutrient solubilization, and siderophore synthesis (Delegan et al., 2021;
 457 Fanai et al., 2024; Mmotla et al., 2025). Although several isolates exhibited very high 16S rRNA sequence
 458 similarity, distinct colony morphologies justified their retention as separate isolates for downstream functional
 459 assays, pending whole-genome sequencing.

460

461 Among all isolates, strain F (*Enterobacter quasihormaechei*) was the most dominant, being detected across
 462 all treatments and reaching a peak relative abundance of 80.98% in the NG5.1 (*Tetraselmis*) treatment. This
 463 dominance coincided with NG5.1 exhibiting the lowest Shannon and Simpson diversity indices, reflecting the
 464 strong prevalence of *E. quasihormaechei*. More broadly, alpha diversity analysis indicated that control
 465 treatments (initial soil, water, and NPK) maintained higher culturable diversity than most algal-treated
 466 microcosms, suggesting that algal supplementation imposes selective pressures on culturable bacterial
 467 communities.

468 Notably, NG5.1 also yielded the highest abundance of culturable bacteria, averaging $25,924.33 \pm 5,029.80$
 469 CFU/mg, in contrast to the initial soil mixture (T0), which exhibited the lowest abundance at 129.81 ± 40.50
 470 CFU/mg (Figure 9). This indicates that NG5.1 supported substantial proliferation of *E. quasihormaechei*, both
 471 in relative proportion and absolute abundance. This pronounced dominance suggests that algal-derived
 472 compounds may create selective niches that favor specific bacterial taxa, leading to strong restructuring of the
 473 culturable soil microbiome.

474

475
 476 **Figure 9** - Abundance of culturable bacteria across microcosm treatments. Column graph displaying the
 477 average (n = 3) colony-forming units (CFUs) per milligram of soil dry weight for algal-supplemented, water,
 478 and NPK (fertiliser) microcosms. Error bars represent ± 1 standard deviation. Data were analysed using one-
 479 way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's post hoc test, with distinct letters indicating statistically significant
 480 differences ($p < 0.05$).
 481
 482
 483

484 This culturomics-based approach enables the isolation of representative strains for functional characterization
485 of plant growth-promoting traits, complementing metabarcoding analyses that capture total community
486 diversity. Integrating these approaches provides a framework for linking community-level shifts with
487 experimentally validated functional traits, facilitating the identification of candidate PGPB for future agricultural
488 applications.

489 **3.8 Effect Over Isolates Growth**

490 Bacterial growth in response to aqueous algal extracts was assessed over 24 h by measuring optical density
491 at 600 nm (OD₆₀₀) (Supplementary Figure 1). All isolates demonstrated the capacity to grow in the presence
492 of algal treatments, although responses varied substantially depending on both the extract and the bacterial
493 strain. Extracts NG4.1 and N14.1, both derived from *Arthrospira* sp., consistently promoted higher bacterial
494 growth compared to other algal treatments and the non-supplemented control across the majority of isolates.
495 This stimulatory effect is consistent with previous reports describing *Arthrospira*-derived biomasses as
496 biostimulatory, likely due to their nutrient-rich composition and diverse bioactive compounds (Begum et al.,
497 2024).

498 In contrast, several algal extracts exhibited inhibitory effects on bacterial proliferation, particularly NG6.1
499 (*Nannochloropsis* sp.), NG5.1 (*Tetraselmis* sp.), and NG7.1 (Terrallgae commercial mix). For example, isolate
500 T (*Bacillus australimaris*) reached an OD₆₀₀ of approximately 1.5 under NG4.1 but plateaued at ~0.5 under
501 NG5.1, illustrating pronounced extract-dependent variation in growth responses. These inhibitory effects may
502 reflect the presence of bioactive or antimicrobial metabolites, including long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids,
503 which have been reported to exert bacteriostatic or bactericidal effects depending on concentration and
504 microbial sensitivity (Zourro et al., 2024; Carrillo and Anchundia, 2024). Importantly, such effects are likely to
505 be highly context- and strain-dependent, and may contribute to selective pressures shaping microbial
506 community composition rather than representing generalized toxicity. Hence, these findings indicate that algal
507 extracts can differentially modulate bacterial growth, promoting or constraining proliferation in a strain- and
508 extract-specific manner. This selective modulation is consistent with the compositional shifts observed in
509 microcosm experiments, supporting a role for algal-derived compounds in shaping microbial community
510 structure through differential growth responses.

511 **3.9 Biofilm production**

512 Biofilm formation, a key trait for bacterial surface attachment and root colonization, exhibited strong intrinsic
513 variability among isolates (Ajijah et al., 2023). In addition to this inherent variability, algal supplementation
514 significantly influenced biofilm formation across all 16 isolates (Supplementary Figure 2), with responses
515 varying in both direction and magnitude depending on the specific extract–strain combination. In general,
516 inhibitory effects predominated, with 104 significant reductions compared to 30 enhancements, indicating that
517 most algal treatments reduced biofilm formation relative to controls. However, these responses were highly
518 context-dependent and varied substantially across isolates and extracts. N14.1 (*Arthrospira* sp.) enhanced
519 biofilm formation in the greatest number of isolates, consistent with its stimulatory effects on bacterial growth.
520 This may reflect its nutrient-rich composition supporting the synthesis of extracellular polymeric substances
521 required for biofilm development (Abdel Latif et al., 2022).

522 In contrast, N13.2 (*Skeletonema* sp.) exhibited the strongest inhibitory effects, reducing biofilm formation in 9
523 of the 16 isolates, suggesting the presence of bioactive compounds that interfere with biofilm development.
524 Importantly, the predominance of inhibitory responses does not necessarily indicate a detrimental effect on
525 plant-associated functions. Biofilm formation is a complex and tightly regulated process, and its reduction
526 under specific conditions may reflect shifts in bacterial lifestyle strategies (e.g., planktonic versus surface-
527 associated growth) or competitive dynamics among strains. As such, modulation of biofilm formation by algal
528 extracts is likely to contribute to selective microbial structuring rather than representing a uniform suppression

529 of functional potential. Collectively, these findings demonstrate that algal supplementation differentially
530 modulates bacterial biofilm formation in a strain- and extract-dependent manner, with potential implications for
531 rhizosphere colonization and plant-microbe interactions.

532 **3.10 Auxins production**

533 Auxin (indole-3-acetic acid, IAA) is a key phytohormone involved in root development and plant growth
534 promotion (Pappalettere et al., 2024). Its production varied significantly among isolates, both intrinsically and
535 in response to algal supplementation. However, compared to other traits, significant responses were less
536 frequent and of lower magnitude, with only 13 increases and 51 decreases observed across all treatment–
537 isolate combinations (Supplementary Figure 3). Algal supplementation induced both stimulatory and inhibitory
538 responses within the same treatment. For example, NG6.1 (*Nannochloropsis* sp.) elicited both increases and
539 decreases in IAA production depending on the isolate, highlighting strong strain-specific effects. In contrast,
540 some extracts, such as NG1.1 (*Chlorella* sp.), had minimal overall impact despite showing more pronounced
541 effects on other traits such as biofilm formation.

542 Notably, no consistent relationship was observed between biofilm formation and auxin production, indicating
543 that these traits are likely regulated independently under the experimental conditions tested. Overall, the
544 relatively limited responsiveness of IAA biosynthesis to algal supplementation suggests that auxin production
545 may be more tightly regulated than other plant growth-promoting traits, and therefore less sensitive to
546 modulation by algal-derived metabolites under the conditions tested.

547 **3.11 Siderophores production**

548 Siderophores are iron-chelating compounds that enhance the acquisition of bioavailable iron and support plant
549 growth under iron-limiting conditions (Li et al., 2023). In contrast to other plant growth-promoting traits,
550 siderophore production was consistently stimulated by algal supplementation across the majority of isolates,
551 with 58 instances of significant increases compared to 27 decreases (Supplementary Figure 4).

552 Among the treatments, AP11.2 (*Ulva* sp.) showed the strongest overall stimulatory effect, significantly
553 increasing siderophore production in 11 of the 16 isolates. Isolate A8 (*Bacillus sanguinis*) exhibited the greatest
554 magnitude of response under this treatment, with more than a four-fold increase relative to the control. Across
555 all isolates, strain T (*Bacillus australimaris*) displayed the highest responsiveness, with significant increases
556 observed under all algal treatments ($p < 0.001$). The consistency and frequency of stimulatory responses
557 distinguish siderophore production from other evaluated traits, which showed more variable or predominantly
558 inhibitory patterns. This suggests that algal-derived compounds may broadly promote bacterial iron acquisition
559 mechanisms, either by acting as metabolic substrates or by modulating regulatory pathways associated with
560 iron limitation.

561 However, while the observed responses are robust, the underlying mechanisms remain unresolved and may
562 involve indirect effects on cellular metabolism or iron availability rather than direct induction of siderophore
563 biosynthesis pathways. Thus, these results indicate that siderophore production represents one of the most
564 consistently enhanced bacterial functions in response to algal supplementation, highlighting it as a key
565 functional axis through which algal extracts may influence plant–microbe interactions.

566 **3.12 Proline production**

567 Proline is an osmoprotectant associated with the stabilization of cellular structures under abiotic stress
568 conditions such as drought and salinity (Zulfiqar and Ashraf, 2023). As with other plant growth-promoting traits,
569 proline production was significantly influenced by algal supplementation. Overall, inhibitory effects
570 predominated, with 149 instances of significant reduction compared to 58 increases across all isolate–
571 treatment combinations (Supplementary Figure 5).

572 The strongest inhibitory effects were observed for treatments NG5.1 (*Tetraselmis* sp.), NG6.1
573 (*Nannochloropsis* sp.), and NG7.1 (Terrallgae), which also corresponded to the most pronounced reductions
574 in bacterial growth observed in growth curve analyses. This convergence suggests that reduced proline
575 production may, at least in part, reflect broader constraints on bacterial metabolism under these treatments.
576 In contrast, AP11.2 (*Ulva* sp.) and N16.2 (*Tisochrysis* sp.) demonstrated more consistent stimulatory effects
577 across multiple isolates, enhancing proline production. These patterns align with their positive effects on
578 siderophore production and bacterial growth, suggesting coordinated modulation of multiple plant growth-
579 promoting traits under specific algal treatments. Importantly, reduced proline production does not necessarily
580 imply diminished plant-beneficial potential, as proline synthesis is typically associated with stress responses
581 and may be downregulated under more favorable growth conditions. Therefore, the observed variation in
582 proline production likely reflects shifts in bacterial physiological state rather than uniform suppression of
583 functional capacity. These findings indicate that algal extracts differentially modulate proline production in a
584 context-dependent manner, with effects linked to broader metabolic responses and growth dynamics.

585 **3.13 Semi-Quantitative Determination of ACC Deaminase**

586 ACC deaminase reduces plant ethylene levels by degrading 1-aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylate (ACC),
587 thereby supporting continued root development and nutrient uptake under stress conditions (Hausinger et al.,
588 2023; Gamalero et al., 2023). Bacterial ACC deaminase activity, inferred from growth using ACC as the sole
589 carbon source, varied markedly across isolates in response to algal supplementation, although the overall
590 trend was towards stimulation (Supplementary Figure 6).

591 Growth was significantly enhanced in approximately 50% of the isolate–treatment combinations (135/272),
592 compared to only 15 significant reductions. NG4.1 (*Arthrospira* sp.) showed the strongest stimulatory effect,
593 enhancing growth in 13 of the 16 isolates, whereas AP11.2 (*Ulva* sp.) exhibited the highest number of inhibitory
594 responses (five). All isolates displayed basal growth on ACC in the absence of algal supplementation,
595 indicating the presence of ACC deaminase activity, although growth levels remained low relative to those
596 observed in nutrient-rich media.

597 Importantly, as this assay infers ACC deaminase activity from bacterial growth, the presence of additional
598 carbon sources in algal extracts may confound interpretation. Enhanced growth may therefore reflect
599 increased metabolic activity supported by exogenous substrates rather than direct upregulation of ACC
600 deaminase activity. Consequently, while the results indicate strong isolate- and treatment-dependent
601 responses, they should be interpreted as indicative of potential modulation of ACC-related metabolism rather
602 than definitive evidence of changes in ACC deaminase enzymatic activity. In general, these findings suggest
603 that algal extracts can influence bacterial growth under ACC-utilizing conditions, although direct enzymatic
604 measurements would be required to confirm specific effects on ACC deaminase activity. Collectively, these
605 functional assays indicate that algal extracts modulate bacterial activity in a trait-specific and context-
606 dependent manner, rather than uniformly enhancing plant growth-promoting functions.

607 **3.14 Associations between fatty acids and bacterial functional traits**

608 Spearman correlation analyses revealed selective and target-dependent associations between fatty acid (FA)
609 composition and bacterial functional readouts, rather than uniform relationships across traits (Annex Tables).
610 Among the most consistent patterns, higher proportions of C15:0 were repeatedly associated with reduced
611 biofilm formation, whereas biomasses enriched in C20:2 n-6 or containing moderate levels of C16:0 tended to
612 support increased biofilm production. These patterns are consistent with a membrane-centric interpretation,
613 whereby shorter or odd-chain saturated fatty acids increase membrane rigidity and may hinder early surface
614 adhesion, while longer or partially unsaturated acyl chains facilitate membrane remodeling and energy supply
615 via β -oxidation, conditions favorable for biofilm development. Such interpretations align with established links
616 between acyl-chain composition, membrane fluidity, and biofilm physiology (Dubois-Brissonnet et al., 2016).

617 For ACC-related responses, positive associations were more frequently observed with n-6 C18–C20 fatty
618 acids, whereas short-chain saturated fatty acids (C14:0–C15:0) tended to correlate with reduced activity. This
619 pattern is consistent with evidence that ACC deaminase-associated metabolism is sensitive to cellular energy
620 and redox balance, including oxygen-dependent regulation in plant-associated bacteria (Singh et al., 2015).
621 Siderophore production showed recurrent positive associations with C18:1 n-9 and, in some cases, C24:0,
622 suggesting that MUFA-rich or neutral-lipid-rich matrices may better support the energetic demands of
623 siderophore biosynthesis. In contrast, auxin and proline responses were highly isolate-dependent, consistent
624 with the notion that exogenous fatty acids can act as nutrients, signaling molecules, or stressors depending
625 on uptake capacity, metabolic routing, and membrane homeostasis.

626 No single fatty acid emerged as a universal predictor of bacterial functional responses. Instead, the data define
627 compositional “windows” associated with specific functional outcomes: biomasses enriched in C15:0 may be
628 less favorable for biofilm formation or ACC-related responses; MUFA-rich or moderately n-6-enriched profiles
629 (e.g., C18:1 n-9, C20:2 n-6) appear more supportive of siderophore production and ACC-associated activity;
630 and very-long-chain saturated fatty acids (C22:0–C24:0) may exert context-dependent effects, particularly for
631 auxin and proline responses. These associations support a mechanistic framework in which fatty acid
632 composition influences bacterial physiology through membrane properties, metabolic routing, and energy
633 availability, thereby shaping functional responses.

634 **3.15 Integration with treatment-level biological responses**

635 When considered alongside treatment-level biological outcomes, the compositional patterns identified in fatty
636 acid (FA) profiles were broadly consistent with observed microbial and functional responses. The most growth-
637 promoting extracts, NG4.1 and N14.1 (both *Arthrospira platensis*), exhibited FA profiles aligned with those
638 associated with enhanced bacterial growth and ACC-related responses, including moderate C16:0 and/or
639 enrichment in n-6 C18–C20 fatty acids such as C20:2 n-6. In contrast, extracts associated with reduced
640 bacterial growth (NG5.1, NG6.1, NG7.1) corresponded to FA profiles predicted to increase membrane rigidity
641 (e.g., short- or odd-chain saturated fatty acids) or to impose metabolic constraints, potentially through
642 increased susceptibility to lipid peroxidation in the case of specific n-6 PUFA. These patterns are consistent
643 with the inhibitory effects observed in both growth and proline assays, suggesting that FA composition
644 contributes to shaping bacterial physiological responses under these treatments. Similarly, the strong and
645 consistent stimulation of siderophore production observed for AP11.2 (*Ulva rigida*) aligned with its enrichment
646 in C18:1 n-9 and, in some cases, C24:0, supporting the association between MUFA-rich profiles and enhanced
647 siderophore biosynthesis. Conversely, certain n-6 PUFA (e.g., C20:3 n-6) were associated with reduced
648 siderophore output, further highlighting the specificity of FA–function relationships. Importantly, these
649 associations should be interpreted as indicative rather than causal, as multiple biochemical components may
650 contribute to the observed biological effects, and interactions between compounds are likely to influence
651 microbial responses. In particular, while FA composition provided a clearer axis for interpreting functional
652 outcomes, other metabolite classes such as VOCs may exert context-dependent or combinatorial effects that
653 are not resolved at the class level.

654 Across traits, responses were consistently strain- and extract-dependent, with no uniform enhancement across
655 all functional readouts. For example, while siderophore production was broadly stimulated, other traits such
656 as auxin production and biofilm formation showed variable or predominantly inhibitory responses. These
657 patterns indicate that algal extracts do not act as generalised stimulants of microbial activity, but rather as
658 selective modulators of specific functional traits and microbial subpopulations. This selective modulation is
659 consistent with the deterministic community assembly patterns observed in microcosm experiments, where
660 algal supplementation promoted reproducible enrichment of specific microbial guilds rather than stochastic
661 community restructuring. Together, these results support a model in which algal extracts act as ecological

662 filters, shaping both microbial composition and functional potential through differential growth responses and
663 metabolic modulation.

664 Finally, it is important to note that several functional responses were inferred from proxy measurements (e.g.,
665 growth-based assays or predictive metagenomics), and therefore represent approximations of microbial
666 activity under the tested conditions. While the overall coherence between chemical composition, microbial
667 shifts, and functional assays strengthens the interpretation, direct mechanistic validation would be required to
668 fully resolve causal relationships. This convergence of chemical composition, microbial community
669 restructuring, and functional responses supports a predictive framework in which algal biomasses can be
670 rationally selected or designed to target specific microbiome functions.

671 **3.16 Plant Test**

672 To evaluate the effects of algal supplementation on tomato growth, three selected extracts - AP11.2 (*Ulva*
673 sp.), N13.3 (*Skeletonema* sp.), and N16.2 (*Tisochrysis* sp.) - were applied under optimized growth conditions
674 in both untreated (original) and heat-sterilized (tyndallized) soils. Clear differences in plant survival were
675 observed between soil types. In original soil, high mortality (50–70%) occurred across treatments, with
676 symptoms consistent with soilborne pathogen infection (Chinheya et al., 2024; Cui et al., 2021; Zhang et al.,
677 2023). The isolation of fungal taxa including *Fusarium longifundum*, *Rhizopus arrhizus*, and *Mucor*
678 *circinelloides* from symptomatic plants further support that pathogen pressure contributed to the observed
679 effects. In contrast, all plants grown in tyndallized soil survived, confirming effective pathogen suppression
680 through sterilization. Despite pathogen pressure, algal treatments significantly improved plant performance. In
681 original soil, all extracts increased root and shoot length relative to controls, with N13.3 and N16.2 also
682 reducing mortality by ~20% (figure X). In tyndallized soil, algal supplementation primarily enhanced shoot
683 length and, for N13.3 and N16.2, significantly increased fresh weight (Supplementary Figure 7 and
684 Supplementary 1).

685 These findings support a dual mode of action for algal extracts: a direct nutritional effect, evident under reduced
686 microbial conditions, and an indirect, microbially mediated or stress-alleviating effect under biotic stress
687 evident in the original soil (Chanthini et al., 2023). Overall, algal supplementation enhanced tomato growth,
688 with the greatest relative benefits observed under biotic stress. This highlights the importance of plant-microbe
689 interactions in mediating algal biostimulant effects and supports their potential as sustainable tools for
690 improving crop resilience. The stronger relative effects observed under non-sterile conditions, together with
691 the microbial and functional shifts described above, are consistent with a microbiome-mediated component
692 contributing to plant performance, although direct causal relationships cannot be fully resolved within this
693 study.

694 **4 Conclusions**

695 Modern agriculture's reliance on synthetic inputs is driving environmental degradation and threatening long-
696 term sustainability, highlighting the need for alternative strategies such as algal-derived biostimulants. In this
697 context, the present study demonstrates that algal biomasses can enhance plant performance through both
698 direct and microbiome-mediated mechanisms. Across 17 phylogenetically and biochemically diverse extracts,
699 algal supplementation selectively restructured soil microbial communities while preserving overall community
700 stability. These shifts were largely governed by deterministic assembly processes, indicating that algal inputs
701 act as consistent ecological filters that promote the enrichment of specific microbial guilds.

702 At the treatment level, clear differences in biological responses were observed. *Arthrospira*-derived extracts
703 (NG4.1 and N14.1) consistently promoted bacterial growth and supported multiple functional traits, while *Ulva*
704 sp. (AP11.2) exhibited the strongest and most consistent stimulation of siderophore production across isolates.

705 In contrast, extracts such as NG5.1 (*Tetraselmis* sp.), NG6.1 (*Nannochloropsis* sp.), and NG7.1 showed more
706 selective or inhibitory effects, highlighting the importance of extract composition in determining microbial
707 outcomes. At the functional level, algal extracts exerted trait-specific and isolate-dependent effects. Among
708 the evaluated traits, siderophore production and ACC-associated responses showed the most consistent
709 stimulation, whereas other functions such as auxin production, biofilm formation, and proline synthesis
710 displayed more variable or context-dependent responses. These findings indicate that algal extracts do not
711 act as generalized stimulants of microbial activity, but rather as selective modulators of specific bacterial
712 functions. Fatty acid composition emerged as a key biochemical axis associated with microbial functional
713 responses, providing a mechanistic link between algal biomass composition and microbiome modulation. In
714 contrast, VOC profiles showed more conserved patterns and weaker associations with functional outcomes,
715 suggesting a more limited role at the class level under the conditions tested.

716 Importantly, plant assays confirmed that algal supplementation improves tomato growth and survival, with the
717 strongest relative effects observed under conditions of high biotic stress. In particular, treatments N13.3
718 (*Skeletonema* sp.) and N16.2 (*Tisochrysis* sp.) reduced plant mortality and enhanced growth under non-sterile
719 conditions, supporting a microbiome-mediated or stress-alleviating effect. Under reduced microbial pressure,
720 algal treatments primarily enhanced growth-related parameters, consistent with direct plant responses. While
721 functional predictions and growth-based assays provide valuable insight into microbiome responses, they
722 represent indirect measures of microbial activity. Therefore, the functional interpretations presented here
723 should be considered indicative, and further mechanistic validation will be required to resolve causal
724 relationships.

725 In summary, this work establishes algal extracts as targeted modulators of soil microbiomes, capable of
726 enhancing beneficial bacterial functions and improving plant performance. These findings support their
727 potential as sustainable tools for reducing reliance on synthetic inputs and advancing microbiome-informed
728 agricultural practices. Importantly, the variability in responses across extracts highlights the need for targeted
729 selection of algal biomasses based on desired microbiome and functional outcomes.

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744 **Author Contributions**

745 Conceptualization, Jelena Vladic and Juan Ignacio Vilchez; methodology, Millia Rose McQuade, Stela Jokic,
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755 supervision, Jelena Vladic and Juan Ignacio Vilchez; project administration, Jelena Vladic and Juan Ignacio
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775 **Competing of Interest**

776 The authors declare no conflicts of interest. The funders had no role in the design of the study; in the collection,
777 analyses, or interpretation of data; in the writing of the manuscript; or in the decision to publish the results.

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960 **Supplementary Figure 1 - Growth analysis of bacterial isolates.** Line graphs display the average (n = 3)
 961 growth patterns of 16 bacterial isolates in LB medium over 24 hours, with and without algal supplementation,
 962 inferred from optical density at 600 nm (OD₆₀₀). Each isolate is displayed in a separate graph, with treatment
 963 conditions indicated by different colours and symbols (as shown in the legend). OD₆₀₀ was measured at 0, 6,
 964 12, and 24 hours, with the initial OD₆₀₀ = 0.05. Error bars represent ± one standard deviation.

965
 966 **Supplementary Figure 2 - Biofilm production of bacterial isolates.** Column graphs show average biofilm production
 967 of 16 bacterial isolates over 24 hours, with and without algal supplementation, measured as optical density at 550 nm
 968 (OD_{550}). Error bars represent \pm one standard deviation ($n = 3$). Data were analysed using a one-way ANOVA followed by
 969 Dunnett's post-hoc test, with statistically significant differences relative to the unsupplemented control indicated by
 970 asterisks (* = $p \leq 0.05$, ** = $p \leq 0.01$, *** = $p \leq 0.001$, **** = $p \leq 0.0001$).

972
 973 **Supplementary Figure 3 - Auxin production of bacterial isolates.** Column graphs show auxin production of 16 bacterial
 974 isolates over 48 hours, with and without algal supplementation, measured as optical density at 530 nm (OD_{530}). Error bars
 975 represent ± 1 standard deviation ($n = 3$). Data were analysed using a one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's post-hoc test,
 976 with statistically significant differences relative to the unsupplemented control indicated by asterisks (* = $p \leq 0.05$, ** = p
 977 ≤ 0.01 , *** = $p \leq 0.001$, **** = $p \leq 0.0001$).

979
 980 **Supplementary Figure 4 - Siderophore production of bacterial isolates.** Column graphs show siderophore production
 981 of 16 bacterial isolates over 16 hours, with and without algal supplementation, measured as percentage siderophore units
 982 (PSU) at 630nm (OD₆₃₀). Error bars represent ± one standard deviation (n = 3). Data were analysed using a one-way
 983 ANOVA followed by Dunnett's post-hoc test, with statistically significant differences relative to the unsupplemented control
 984 indicated by asterisks (* = $p \leq 0.05$, ** = $p \leq 0.01$, *** = $p \leq 0.001$, **** = $p \leq 0.0001$).

987
 988 **Figure 5 - Proline production of bacterial isolates.** Column graphs show proline production (mM) of 16 bacterial isolates
 989 over two days, with and without algal supplementation, measured at optical density at 520 nm (OD₅₂₀). Error bars represent
 990 ± one standard deviation (n = 3). Data were analysed using a one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's post-hoc test, with
 991 statistically significant differences relative to the unsupplemented control indicated by asterisks (* = p ≤ 0.05, ** = p ≤
 992 0.01, *** = p ≤ 0.001, **** = p ≤ 0.0001).

994
 995 **Figure 6 - ACC consumption (indirect deaminase activity determination) of bacterial isolates.** Column graphs show
 996 ACC deaminase activity of 16 bacterial isolates over 3 days, with and without algal supplementation, inferred from growth
 997 at 600 nm (OD_{600}) with ACC as the sole carbon source. Error bars represent \pm one standard deviation ($n = 3$). Data were
 998 analysed using a one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's post-hoc test, with statistically significant differences relative to
 999 the unsupplemented control indicated by asterisks ($* = p \leq 0.05$, $** = p \leq 0.01$, $*** = p \leq 0.001$, $**** = p \leq 0.0001$).

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1004 **Figure 7. Phenotypic analysis of tomato seedlings under algal application in tyndallized and original soils.**

1005 Representative triplicates of plants grown in original and tyndallized tomato field soil under different treatments: (a, e)

1006 untreated control; (b, f) AP11.2 extract; (c, g) N13.3 extract; and (d, h) N16.2 extract. Column graphs show mean (i)

1007 root length (cm), (j) shoot length (cm), and (k) dry weight (g) of early-stage tomato plants (n = 3). Statistical analysis was

1008 performed using two-way ANOVA to assess the effects of soil type, algal treatment, and their interaction, followed by

1009 Tukey's multiple comparisons test. Blue asterisks indicate significant differences relative to the original soil water control,

1010 while purple asterisks indicate significant differences relative to the tyndallized soil water control.

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1019 **Supplementary Table 1 - Fold changes in plant growth parameters under algal supplementation relative to water**
1020 **controls.** Approximate fold changes in root length (cm), shoot length (cm), and fresh weight (g) were calculated for each
1021 algal treatment (AP11.2, N13.3, and N16.2) relative to the corresponding soil-specific water control (original or tyndallized
1022 soil).

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	Root Length		Shoot Length		Fresh weight	
	Original	Tyndallized	Original	Tyndallized	Original	Tyndallized
AP11.2	3.85	0.91	1.92	1.38	2.89	1.86
N13.3	4.89	0.87	2.21	1.45	5.64	3.16
N16.2	4.88	0.67	2.21	1.33	5.30	2.48

1024 ANNEX

1025 Table A1. Fatty acid composition determined by GC-FID

Sample	AP 10.2	NG 1.1	NG2.1	NG3.1	NG4.1	NG5.1	NG6.1	NG7.1	NG8.1	N13.2	N13.3	N14.1	N15.1	N16.2	N33.1	IA9.1	AP11.2
C4:0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
C6:0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
C8:0	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.14±0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
C10:0	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.11±0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
C11:0	-	-	-	-	1.83±0.36	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
C12:0	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.23±0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.21±0.00	-	-
C13:0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
C14:0	11.42±0.18	0.35±0.02	3.39±0.15	0.99±0.01	0.17±0.00	0.94±0.03	4.12±0.03	0.75±0.01	0.76±0.02	25.04±0.11	28.37±0.52	0.23±0.00	0.38±0.01	25.18±0.18	29.53±0.07	5.56±0.04	2.90±0.01
C14:1	0.17±0.00	-	-	-	-	-	0.06±0.00	-	-	-	0.94±0.04	-	-	0.23±0.04	-	-	-
C15:0	0.63±0.04	0.16±0.01	0.61±0.13	0.55±0.01	0.10±0.00	0.17±0.04	0.42±0.00	0.26±0.01	0.27±0.01	1.35±0.01	0.68±0.02	0.11±0.01	0.29±0.02	1.19±0.01	1.20±0.01	-	-
C15:1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
C16:0	19.23±0.66	34.93±0.39	31.66±0.11	24.34±0.18	52.21±0.03	40.45±0.11	19.89±0.11	23.23±0.01	41.20±0.09	15.19±1.28	10.60±0.08	45.78±0.02	20.19±0.54	14.99±0.01	23.61±0.04	49.99±0.37	37.89±0.00
C16:1	1.31±0.03	3.25±0.05	12.40±0.37	2.22±0.00	6.12±0.05	1.83±0.02	21.68±0.02	13.01±0.01	1.74±0.00	44.11±0.13	42.05±0.21	7.25±0.02	1.67±0.12	14.41±0.04	17.99±0.07	-	9.50±0.00
C17:0	0.32±0.01	0.40±0.00	0.39±0.05	0.72±0.01	0.31±0.00	0.18±0.00	0.41±0.00	0.42±0.01	0.52±0.01	-	-	0.27±0.00	1.05±0.08	0.18±0.01	0.26±0.01	-	-
C17:1	0.96±0.13	3.19±0.17	2.60±0.04	1.86±0.01	0.62±0.01	2.63±0.09	0.85±0.03	14.29±0.04	3.22±0.05	2.03±0.81	1.62±0.21	0.60±0.11	14.58±0.76	1.12±0.14	0.27±0.01	4.83±0.41	-
C18:0	2.08±0.13	3.84±0.04	1.59±0.24	0.70±0.03	1.26±0.01	0.85±0.02	0.22±0.01	1.60±0.01	2.90±0.06	2.55±0.57	1.78±0.00	1.02±0.01	1.90±0.04	0.40±0.10	0.72±0.01	5.79±0.35	4.00±0.05
C18:1 n9c+t	38.36±1.52	22.26±0.40	19.92±0.22	7.10±0.04	1.22±0.04	11.46±0.07	6.10±0.01	4.37±0.01	14.00±0.20	1.14±0.18	1.77±0.01	1.83±0.05	6.92±0.19	8.60±0.08	0.99±0.00	9.86±0.30	13.70±0.14
C18:2 n6c	4.65±0.13	23.51±0.48	5.89±0.75	6.37±0.01	17.31±0.18	6.22±0.04	2.79±0.04	17.68±0.01	17.53±0.29	0.98±0.01	2.02±0.04	18.42±0.06	25.34±0.09	8.57±0.01	1.10±0.01	6.39±0.62	3.10±0.09
C18:2 n6t	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.91±0.04
C18:3 n6	0.62±0.06	0.13±0.06	0.84±0.11	0.87±0.01	17.94±0.10	3.20±0.04	0.16±0.01	-	1.10±0.03	1.38±0.69	1.57±0.01	21.48±0.20	0.33±0.11	1.34±0.02	3.63±0.01	-	-
C18:3 n3	3.61±0.21	5.45±0.24	10.57±0.54	51.17±0.07	0.49±0.01	24.74±0.04	0.26±0.01	22.40±0.01	13.19±0.08	-	-	2.02±0.12	25.83±0.23	10.15±0.04	0.88±0.03	-	9.47±0.54
C20:0	0.68±0.03	0.60±0.05	-	-	0.10±0.01	1.28±0.12	-	0.17±0.01	0.95±0.02	-	-	0.07±0.00	0.21±0.01	3.25±0.06	-	-	-
C20:1	0.25±0.03	0.25±0.01	1.56±0.15	0.13±0.00	-	1.69±0.01	0.10±0.01	0.11±0.01	0.59±0.05	-	-	0.05±0.01	0.19±0.04	-	-	-	-

C20:2	0.25±0	0.09±0		0.09±0	0.18±0	0.21±0	0.24±0	0.11±0	0.20±0			0.20±0	0.11±0	0.51±0			
n6	.01	.01	-	.04	.03	.01	.00	.00	.01	-	-	.00	.06	.16	-	-	-
C20:3	0.28±0						0.15±0					0.15±0			0.29±0		
n6	.01	-	-	-	-	-	.00	-	-	-	-	.01	-	-	.00	-	-
C21:0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
C20:4	9.10±0		1.40±0	0.24±0		0.52±0	5.91±0	0.33±0				0.11±0	0.37±0	0.21±0	2.25±0	10.40±	3.89±0
n6	.18	-	.13	.00	-	.00	.01	.01	-	-	-	.01	.04	.01	.01	0.33	.12
C20:3				0.09±0									0.06±0				
n3	-	-	-	.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	.00	-	-	-	-
C20:5	2.94±0	0.13±0	6.50±0	0.39±0		3.36±0	36.15±	0.89±0		3.85±0	7.20±0	0.24±0	0.24±0	0.65±0	15.13±	7.19±1	3.10±0
n3	.13	.03	.49	.01	-	.01	0.06	.01	-	.16	.01	.00	.06	.04	0.13	.53	.13
	0.57±0	0.46±0		0.41±0			0.06±0	0.14±0	0.22±0	0.67±0	1.42±0	0.05±0	0.15±0	0.23±0	0.48±0		0.84±0
C22:0	.01	.04	-	.00	-	-	.00	.00	.02	.06	.09	.01	.01	.01	.04	-	.04
C22:1	0.40±0																
n9	.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
C22:2		0.13±0		1.04±0		0.31±0			1.45±0								
n6	-	.01	-	.02	-	.01	-	-	.08	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		0.11±0															
C23:0	-	.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	1.14±0	0.81±0		0.43±0				0.14±0	0.21±0			0.09±0	0.24±0	8.84±0			
C24:0	.13	.01	-	.01	-	-	-	.01	.01	-	-	.01	.01	.12	-	-	-
C22:6	1.07±0														1.22±0		
n3	.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	.01	-	-
			0.73±0	0.28±0	0.17±0			0.16±0		1.65±0		0.09±0			0.27±0		
C24:1	-	-	.11	.04	.01	-	-	.02	-	.06	-	.01	-	-	.07	-	-
SFA	36.06	41.625	5	28.13	55.97	43.86	25.58	26.68	5	44.78	42.84	47.6	24.38	54.24	56	5	45.63
			37.62	11.58			28.77			48.92					19.51	14.68	
MUFA	41.44	28.94	37.19	5	8.12	17.6	5	31.92	19.54	5	46.37	9.8	23.35	24.35	5	5	23.2
PUFA-					35.42	10.44		18.11				40.34					
n6	14.89	23.855	8.12	8.595	5	5	9.245	5	20.27	2.35	3.585	5	26.14	10.62	7.265	16.79	7.9
PUFA-			17.06				28.09		23.28			13.18					
n3	7.61	5.58	5	51.65	0.485	5	36.4	5	5	3.85	7.2	2.255	26.13	10.79	17.22	7.19	12.57

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Table A2. Volatile compounds isolated by HS-SPME and analyzed by GC-MS

Compound	Rt	RI	AP10 .2	NG1. 1	NG2. 1	NG3. 1	NG4. 1	NG5. 1	NG6. 1	NG7. 1	NG8. 1	N13. 2	N13. 3	N14. 1	N15. 1	N16. 2	N33. 1	IA9. 1	AP11 .2
ALCOHOLS																			
Ethanol	1.523	< 700	0.46	0.22	0.26	0.64	0.75	0.33	0.34	0.79	0.37	0.44	0.57	-	1.93	0.43	0.63	2.29	0.29
Pentan-1-ol	2.509	769	0.09	3.09	1.67	-	0.22	1.08	1.14	-	-	0.07	-	0.37	0.3	-	-	-	-
Hex-1-en-3-ol	2.614	781										1.57	2.75	-	-	-	1.87	-	
Hexan-1-ol	3.762	874	-	-	-	0.08	3.91	-	-	0.09	0.25	0.99	0.52	3.16	-	-	-	0.06	
(Z)-Octa-1,5-dien-3-ol	5.97	977										2.12	3.41	0.28	-	11.2 1	5.43	-	0.12
Oct-1-en-3-ol	6.102	982	9.56	3.48	-	3.29	0.12	4.68	4.93	3.1	4.22	-	2.63	0.81	-	2.61	5.22	12.2 9	11.25
2-Ethylhexan-1-ol	7.595	103 3										-	-	3.47	1.28	-	-	5.99	
2,6-Dimethylcyclohexanol	10.38 8	111 0	3.3	0.78	17.2 8	18.1 8	14.7 9	15.5	16.3 5	12.1 3	12.3 8	4.77	8.52	22.6 1	17.9 1	10.5 3	12	3.93	2.9
CARBOXYLIC ACIDS																			
Acetic acid	1.66	< 700	0.16	0.11	0.82	0.14	0.07	0.03	0.03	0.31	0.2	-	-	-	0.31	-	-	-	
Butanoic acid	2.588	778	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.41	0.53	0.21	-	-	1.48	-	-	-	
3-Methylbutanoic acid	3.181	834	0.28	1.5	-	-	0.21	-	-	-	0.67	0.4	0.23	-	1.41	0.66	-	-	0.19
2-Methylbutanoic acid	3.323	845	0.25	0.31	-	-	0.05	-	-	1.42	0.25	-	-	-	0.85	-	-	-	0.26
Pentanoic acid	3.827	878	-	0.64	-	-	-	-	-	0.81	-	-	-	-	0.43	0.29	-	-	-
4-Methylpentanoic acid	5.232	949	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.37	-								-
4-Methylpentanoic acid	5.469	958	-	-	-	-	0.1	-	-	0.46	-	-	-	-	-	0.18	-	-	0.08
Hexanoic acid	6.206	985	8.24	22.7 8	-	1.66	1.65	-	-	6.81	-	-	-	-	4.23	-	-	-	3.2
Heptanoic acid	9.334	108 3	3.29	3.1	-	-	-	-	-	0.73	-	2.74	2.53	-	-	-	-	-	3.5
Octanoic acid	13.08 6	118 1	1.93	0.83	-	-	-	-	-	1.15	1.15	0.71	1.24	-	-	0.69	-	-	2.9
Nonanoic acid	17.13 7	127 8	2.37	0.79	-	0.31	-	-	-	0.33	0.79	0.33	-	-	0.17	-	-	1.59	2.8
Decanoic acid	21.12 2	137 4	0.54	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.1	0.08	-	-	-	-	0.12	0.48	-	0.22
Dodecanoic acid	28.92 5	156 8	0.22	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.06	-	-	-	1.27	-	0.32	-	1	0.15

Tetradecanoic acid	36.28 4	176 9										0.4	0.13	-	-	3.15	0.51	-	
HYDROCARBONS																			
Hexane	1.727	< 700	0.24	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.15
p-Xylene	3.806	877	0.27	-	-	0.51	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.53	-	0.22
Tetradecane	22.28 7	140 0	-	-	0.15	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.21	-	-	-	0.03
Pentadec-1-ene	26.00 7	149 2	0.1	-	-	-	-	0.09	0.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.1
Pentadecane	26.31 4	150 0	0.85	-	-	0.84	0.73	-	-	0.21	-	-	-	1.11	0.21	0.22	-	-	0.4
Hexadecane	30.17 4	160 0	-	-	-	0.87	1.06	-	-	0.14	-	-	-	-	0.17	-	-	0.62	0.51
Heptadec-8-ene	33.07 1	167 9	0.18	-	-	2.39	0.46	0.09	0.1	0.93	1.94	-	-	0.55	0.94	-	-	-	0.22
Heptadecane	33.86	170 0	0.26	-	0.46	12.0 2	27.3 3	0.16	0.16	0.95	0.32	0.24	-	27.3 8	1.87	-	-	-	0.18
ALDEHYDES																			
3-Methylbutanal	1.911	< 700	0.03	0.2	-	0.41	0.11	0.14	0.15	0.43	0.41	0.3	0.8	-	0.56	0.52	0.51	0.11	0.13
Pentanal	2.069	< 700	0.24	1.34	0.53	0.84	0.15	0.23	0.25	0.51	0.46	0.21	0.34	-	1.18	0.48	0.2	0.59	0.33
(E)-Pent-2-enal	2.438	761	0.09	0.11	-	0.26	0.06	0.13	0.14	0.17	0.2	0.09	-	-	-	0.14	-	-	0.08
Hexanal	2.822	801	2.13	11.1 2	1.36	0.93	1.16	1.89	1.99	3.29	1.02	0.71	1.06	0.31	4.1	1.44	0.95	4.37	2.8
2-Methylpent-2-enal	3.223	837	-	-	-	0.14	-	0.21	0.22	-	-	-	0.37	-	-	-	-	-	
(E)-Hex-2-enal	3.496	857	0.1	0.22	0.33	0.77	0.1	0.46	0.48	0.28	0.46	0.44	0.52	-	0.3	0.54	0.42	0.43	0.1
(Z)-Hept-4-enal	4.26	901	-	-	0.46	0.27	-	0.31	0.33	-	0.66	-	-	-	0.17	0.3	0.17	-	
Heptanal	4.292	902	0.5	1.73	0.37	0.28	0.22	0.3	0.32	0.77	0.5	1.76	1.72	0.14	0.78	0.47	0.51	1.32	0.6
(E)-Hept-2-enal	5.513	960	0.41	0.27	-	-	0.07	-	-	0.25	-	0.34	0.23	-	0.38	0.18	0.15	1.62	0.39
Octanal	6.762	100 4	0.62	2.57	0.7	0.5	0.12	0.55	0.58	0.56	0.63	0.64	0.43	-	-	-	-	0.89	0.71
(E,E)-Hepta-2,4-dienal	7.015	101 3	0.47	0.29	1.32	0.82	0.12	0.64	0.67	0.39	0.94	0.4	0.33	-	0.62	0.69	0.32	0.54	0.28
(E)-Oct-2-enal	8.526	106 2	1.27	0.97	-	-	0.31	-	-	1.35	-	0.87	-	-	-	-	-	3.57	1.78
Nonanal	10.18 6	110 5	1.52	4.06	1.25	0.68	-	0.16	0.16	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.2
(E,Z)-Nona-2,6-dienal	12.07 3	115 7	0.29	0.03	0.39	0.13	0.06	0.5	0.52	0.1	0.71	1.14	0.62	-	-	0.67	0.83	1.48	0.24
(E)-Non-2-enal	12.32 7	116 3	0.74	0.07	-	0.06	0.23	0.21	0.22	0.26	0.42	0.66	0.37	-	-	-	-	0.86	0.87

Decanal	14.20 3	120 6	0.12	0.34	0.82	0.14	0.26	0.14	0.15	0.15	0.16	-	-	-	0.19	-	-	0.36	0.1
(<i>E,E</i>)-Nona-2,4-dienal	14.54 3	121 5	0.4	0.83	-	-	0.09	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.05	-	-	0.26	0.32
(<i>E</i>)-Dec-2-enal	16.52 6	126 4	0.89	0.63	-	-	-	-	-	0.05	0.55	0.8	-	-	0.38	0.63	-	-	0.98
(<i>E,Z</i>)-Deca-2,4-dienal	17.87 5	129 4	0.83	0.11	-	-	0.36	-	-	0.19	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.54
(<i>E,E</i>)-Deca-2,4-dienal	18.83	131 8	1.53	1.3	-	-	0.41	0.09	0.1	0.05	0.37	-	2.21	-	0.42	0.34	-	1.28	1.2
Dodecanal	22.66 1	140 9										0.36	-	-	-	-	-	-	
ESTERS																			
Ethyl but-2-enoate	3.347	847	-	-	-	-	0.11	-	-	2.12	-								
Ethyl 3-hydroxybutyrate	4.985	938	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.58	-								
Ethyl hexanoate	6.634	999	0.88	0.07	-	0.46	0.22	0.17	0.18	0.75	0.13	-	0.73	-	0.52	-	-	-	0.58
Ethyl octanoate	13.85 9	119 8	0.18	0.03	-	0.01	0.02	0.22	0.23	0.2	0.38	0.14	0.4	-	-	-	-	-	0.11
Methyl tetradecanoate	34.74 2	172 5	1.38	-	-	0.45	-	-	-	0.49	0.53	0.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.28
Ethyl tetradecanoate	37.21 9	179 5										1.2	1.16	-	-	1	0.47	-	
KETONES																			
Heptan-2-one	4.087	892	0.1	0.34	-	0.09	0.22	-	-	0.69	0.16	-	0.2	0.41	0.4	-	0.21	0.49	
6-Methylheptan-2-one	5.467	958	0.06	-	-	0.37	0.1	0.25	0.26	0.46	0.2	0.21	0.53	0.25	-	0.18	0.3	-	0.11
Octan-2-one	6.414	992	0.01	0.03	-	0.06	0.11	0.03	0.03	1.95	0.51	0.97	1.18	0.58	-	-	-	-	0.02
2,2,6-Trimethylcyclohexanone	7.805	104 0	0.37	-	0.54	2.86	0.44	1.19	1.25	1.67	2.18	0.37	1.75	2.07	1.34	1.21	1.63	-	0.15
(<i>E</i>)-Oct-3-en-2-one	7.891	104 3	0.79	3.59	-	-	0.28	-	-	1.15	-	0.11	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.82
(<i>E,E</i>)-Octa-3,5-dien-2-one	8.978	107 4	2.92	2.03	0.93	3.7	1.1	11.4 1	12.0 4	5	3.48	4.3	6.34	0.68	5.86	8.09	8.28	4.31	3.2
(<i>E,Z</i>)-Octa-3,5-dien-2-one	9.79	109 5	3.75	10.3 4	10.1 6	10.4 1	0.2	12.8 1	13.5 1	14.1 9	5.33	5.1	4.86	1.21	10.0 5	9.23	7.52	1.86	2.9
(<i>E</i>)-Non-3-en-2-one	11.53 5	114 3	0.16	0.18	-	0.18	0.06	0.22	0.23	0.23	0.22	0.4	0.56	-	-	-	-	-	
3,5-Nonadien-2-one isomer [*]	12.63 5	141 7										9.13	8.78	-	-	-	7.25	-	0.22
3,5-Nonadien-2-one isomer [*]	13.67 4	119 4										8.22	6.84	-	-	-	7.69	-	
Benzenoid derivatives																			
Benzaldehyde	5.691	967	0.09	1.09	0.79	1.77	0.54	0.76	0.8	3.06	1.02	1.47	1.72	2.03	4.21	2.96	2.34	2.52	0.11
Benzeneacetaldehyde	8.12	105 0	0.33	-	-	-	0.43	-	-	0.42	0.98	0.2	0.19	-	-	0.91	0.17	1.16	0.18

1-Phenylethanone (Acetophenone)	8.871	107 1	0.18	-	-	1.53	0.39	2.1	2.21	0.32	4.42	0.4	-	-	-	-	-	5.2	0.05
APOCAROTENOIDS AND OTHER OXYGENATED TERPENOIDS																			
6-Methylhept-5-en-2-one	6.307	989	0.95	3.05	9.89	0.94	0.46	7.22	7.61	1.52	1.42	0.43	0.63	1.5	1.91	2.27	0.95	2.06	0.75
Fenchone	9.654	109 1	0.99	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.53	0.78	0.3	0.75	0.28	0.75	3.71	0.8
6-Methylhepta-3,5-dien-2-one	10.22 7	110 6	-	-	-	0.74	0.78	0.94	0.99	1.62	1.45	0.93	1.47	0.68	2.2	1.71	1.22	1.46	
2,6,6-Trimethylcyclohex-2-ene-1,4-dione (4-Oxoisophorone)	11.72 6	114 8	0.53	0.72	0.51	1.52	0.68	0.56	0.59	1.44	1.57	1.72	1.49	0.6	1.14	0.29	0.59	0.06	
Safranal	13.98	120 0	0.18	0.78	0.42	1.15	1.58	0.66	0.7	1.17	2.47	0.4	0.4	0.42	1.81	1.16	0.27	-	0.2
β-Cyclocitral	14.83 9	122 3	0.75	0.94	1.47	2.21	1.75	1.88	1.98	1.09	1.09	0.31	1.15	1.74	3.63	3.85	1.16	0.44	0.91
α-Ionone	23.42 5	142 9	0.39	0.16	6.61	3.1	0.51	7.79	8.22	2.89	7.29	-	-	0.34	4.6	-	-	7.18	0.74
(E)-Geranylacetone	24.44 5	145 5	0.24	0.36	0.33	0.29	0.93	0.2	0.21	0.25	0.42	-	-	-	0.64	-	-	-	
7,8-Epoxy-α-ionone	25.03 6	146 9	0.07	-	0.43	0.27	-	0.38	0.4	0.19	0.58	-	-	-	0.15	-	-	0.6	0.17
β-Ionone	25.76 9	148 7	3.33	0.72	16.8 1	12.6 4	22.3 5	11.6 6	12.3	5.38	12.3	8.08	9.8	16.5 3	9.1	6.19	7.07	5.57	3.2
Dihydroactinidiolide	27.42 3	152 9	2.81	0.2	6.19	3.6	7.96	3.77	3.97	3.16	6.45	3.14	2.62	5.54	3.9	4.83	3.21	5.73	3.09
Hexahydrofarnesyl acetone	38.91 8	184 6	0.1	-	0.29	1.91	0.12	0.2	0.21	0.38	1.34	8.18	3.09	0.17	0.15	0.52	0.47	-	0.09
OTHERS																			
Dimethyl sulfide	1.603	< 700	-	-	1.86	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.18	-	-	0.8	-	-	0.05
Diisobutyl phthalate	39.69	186 9	0.47	-	-	0.34	-	0.25	0.26	0.17	0.4	-	0.47	-	-	-	0.18	0.43	0.32

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Table A3. Spearman correlation coefficients between individual fatty acids and biofilm formation.

Fatty Acid	A - not identified	A8 - Bacillus sanguinis	B4 - Exiguobacterium acetylicum	Bd - Exiguobacterium acetylicum	Bl - Exiguobacterium acetylicum	E - Peribacillus frigoritolerans	F - Enterobacter quasihorae	Gw - Priestia aryabhattai	Gy - Peribacillus frigoritolerans	H - Leclercia adecarboxylata	K - Enterobacter quasihorae	P - Priestia aryabhattai	Q - not identified	T - Bacillus australimaris	V - not identified	Z - Priestia megaterium
C10:0	-0.12	0.37	0.19	0.19	0.25	0.31	0.19	0.0	0.19	-0.37	0.0	0.37	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.31
C11:0	-0.19	0.06	0.31	0.25	0.31	0.25	-0.31	0.19	0.12	0.37	0.43	0.06	0.25	-0.25	0.25	0.19
C12:0	0.11	0.08	0.06	-0.15	0.02	-0.05	0.31	0.3	-0.11	-0.29	0.08	-0.01	-0.07	-0.2	0.31	-0.05
C14:0	-0.04	-0.29	-0.13	-0.3	-0.2	-0.34	0.47	0.29	-0.21	-0.17	-0.02	-0.22	-0.39	0.06	0.22	-0.06
C14:1	0.03	0.33	0.1	0.13	-0.02	0.29	0.32	0.22	0.29	0.07	-0.19	0.35	-0.19	0.49	0.33	0.29
C15:0	-0.18	-0.41	-0.72	-0.61	-0.6	-0.56	0.04	0.06	-0.61	0.05	-0.05	-0.05	-0.74	0.28	0.38	-0.61
C16:0	0.22	-0.01	0.42	0.26	0.56	0.21	-0.13	0.04	0.27	0.04	0.34	-0.09	0.62	-0.54	-0.21	0.23
C16:1	-0.28	0.19	-0.1	-0.15	-0.3	-0.11	0.1	0.1	-0.19	0.04	-0.04	0.18	-0.39	0.49	0.23	0.01
C17:0	-0.06	-0.01	-0.47	-0.14	-0.06	-0.17	-0.41	-0.22	-0.28	0.05	0.1	-0.04	-0.15	-0.14	-0.07	-0.51
C17:1	-0.22	-0.16	-0.39	-0.04	-0.2	-0.44	-0.51	-0.5	-0.25	0.09	0.08	0.01	-0.02	0.25	-0.19	-0.32
C18:0	0.14	-0.16	0.12	0.54	0.2	-0.18	-0.43	-0.29	-0.09	-0.27	-0.1	-0.35	0.36	0.01	-0.07	0.16
C18:1 n9c+t	0.05	0.01	0.02	0.17	0.41	0.1	0.2	-0.23	0.2	-0.26	0.04	-0.18	0.15	-0.21	-0.47	0.12
C18:2 n6c	0.19	0.2	0.05	0.15	-0.05	0.19	-0.36	-0.41	0.38	0.11	0.12	0.24	0.4	0.05	-0.27	0.01
C18:2 n6t	0.12	0.19	0.43	0.43	0.37	0.37	0.37	0.12	0.25	-0.43	-0.31	-0.37	0.19	-0.31	-0.31	0.43
C18:3 n3	-0.03	-0.05	-0.42	-0.3	-0.14	-0.11	-0.01	-0.12	-0.18	0.14	-0.14	-0.15	-0.27	-0.23	-0.37	-0.49
C18:3 n6	0.34	-0.12	-0.07	-0.25	-0.14	0.1	0.02	0.41	-0.09	0.48	-0.08	0.28	-0.1	0.03	0.58	-0.21
C20:0	0.19	0.13	-0.07	0.0	-0.11	0.09	-0.1	-0.15	0.26	0.17	0.03	0.46	0.27	0.15	0.06	-0.13
C20:1	-0.01	0.08	-0.39	-0.14	0.05	-0.1	-0.21	-0.27	-0.24	0.14	-0.09	0.05	-0.16	0.0	-0.22	-0.39
C20:2 n6	0.11	0.35	0.09	0.02	0.08	0.42	0.14	-0.04	0.46	0.0	0.03	0.76	0.33	0.18	0.08	0.13
C20:3 n3	-0.07	-0.37	-0.51	-0.33	-0.3	-0.1	-0.03	-0.01	-0.33	0.01	-0.35	-0.32	-0.46	-0.29	-0.1	-0.46
C20:3 n6	0.37	0.18	0.16	-0.19	-0.09	0.12	0.29	0.2	0.09	-0.2	-0.01	0.16	0.07	-0.09	0.23	0.02
C20:4 n6	-0.01	0.14	0.37	-0.1	0.11	0.1	0.52	-0.08	0.24	-0.36	0.1	-0.32	0.06	-0.38	-0.49	0.28
C20:5 n3	-0.14	0.08	0.14	-0.15	-0.07	-0.14	0.38	0.16	-0.12	-0.09	-0.03	-0.17	-0.3	0.11	0.04	0.15
C22:0	0.13	-0.24	-0.32	0.02	-0.2	-0.22	0.16	0.36	-0.37	-0.25	-0.53	-0.3	-0.39	0.07	0.33	-0.24
C22:1 n9																
C22:2 n6	0.1	-0.34	-0.42	-0.04	0.37	-0.19	-0.02	0.37	-0.33	0.03	-0.17	-0.02	-0.01	-0.35	0.15	-0.45
C22:6 n3	0.31	-0.31	-0.12	-0.43	-0.25	-0.43	0.25	0.43	-0.37	0.0	0.12	-0.43	-0.25	-0.43	0.31	-0.43
C23:0																
C24:0	0.05	-0.17	-0.48	-0.26	-0.34	-0.13	-0.08	-0.21	0.02	-0.06	-0.08	0.15	-0.1	0.07	-0.16	-0.39

C24:1	-0.51	-0.37	-0.45	-0.55	-0.37	-0.49	-0.33	-0.14	-0.56	0.27	0.38	-0.21	-0.44	-0.06	-0.14	-0.47
C8:0	-0.12	0.37	0.19	0.19	0.25	0.31	0.19	0.0	0.19	-0.37	0.0	0.37	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.31

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1043 **Table A4.** Spearman correlation coefficients between individual fatty acids and biofilm formation.

Fatty Acid	A - not identified	A8 - Bacillus sanguinis	B4 - Exiguobacterium acetylicum	Bd - Exiguobacterium acetylicum	Bl - Exiguobacterium acetylicum	E - Peribacillus frigoritolerans	F - Enterobacter quasihormaechei	Gw - Priestia aryabhattai	Gy - Peribacillus frigoritolerans	H - Leclercia adecarboxylata	K - Enterobacter quasihormaechei	P - Priestia aryabhattai	Q - not identified	T - Bacillus australimaris	V - not identified	Z - Priestia megaterium
C10:0	-0.12	0.37	0.19	0.19	0.25	0.31	0.19	0.0	0.19	-0.37	0.0	0.37	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.31
C11:0	-0.19	0.06	0.31	0.25	0.31	0.25	-0.31	0.19	0.12	0.37	0.43	0.06	0.25	-0.25	0.25	0.19
C12:0	0.11	0.08	0.06	-0.15	0.02	-0.05	0.31	0.3	-0.11	-0.29	0.08	-0.01	-0.07	-0.2	0.31	-0.05
C14:0	-0.04	-0.29	-0.13	-0.3	-0.2	-0.34	0.47	0.29	-0.21	-0.17	-0.02	-0.22	-0.39	0.06	0.22	-0.06
C14:1	0.03	0.33	0.1	0.13	-0.02	0.29	0.32	0.22	0.29	0.07	-0.19	0.35	-0.19	0.49	0.33	0.29
C15:0	-0.18	-0.41	-0.72	-0.61	-0.6	-0.56	0.04	0.06	-0.61	0.05	-0.05	-0.05	-0.74	0.28	0.38	-0.61
C16:0	0.22	-0.01	0.42	0.26	0.56	0.21	-0.13	0.04	0.27	0.04	0.34	-0.09	0.62	-0.54	-0.21	0.23
C16:1	-0.28	0.19	-0.1	-0.15	-0.3	-0.11	0.1	0.1	-0.19	0.04	-0.04	0.18	-0.39	0.49	0.23	0.01
C17:0	-0.06	-0.01	-0.47	-0.14	-0.06	-0.17	-0.41	-0.22	-0.28	0.05	0.1	-0.04	-0.15	-0.14	-0.07	-0.51
C17:1	-0.22	-0.16	-0.39	-0.04	-0.2	-0.44	-0.51	-0.5	-0.25	0.09	0.08	0.01	-0.02	0.25	-0.19	-0.32
C18:0	0.14	-0.16	0.12	0.54	0.2	-0.18	-0.43	-0.29	-0.09	-0.27	-0.1	-0.35	0.36	0.01	-0.07	0.16
C18:1n9c+t	0.05	0.01	0.02	0.17	0.41	0.1	0.2	-0.23	0.2	-0.26	0.04	-0.18	0.15	-0.21	-0.47	0.12
C18:2n6c	0.19	0.2	0.05	0.15	-0.05	0.19	-0.36	-0.41	0.38	0.11	0.12	0.24	0.4	0.05	-0.27	0.01
C18:2n6t	0.12	0.19	0.43	0.43	0.37	0.37	0.37	0.12	0.25	-0.43	-0.31	-0.37	0.19	-0.31	-0.31	0.43
C18:3n3	-0.03	-0.05	-0.42	-0.3	-0.14	-0.11	-0.01	-0.12	-0.18	0.14	-0.14	-0.15	-0.27	-0.23	-0.37	-0.49
C18:3n6	0.34	-0.12	-0.07	-0.25	-0.14	0.1	0.02	0.41	-0.09	0.48	-0.08	0.28	-0.1	0.03	0.58	-0.21
C20:0	0.19	0.13	-0.07	0.0	-0.11	0.09	-0.1	-0.15	0.26	0.17	0.03	0.46	0.27	0.15	0.06	-0.13
C20:1	-0.01	0.08	-0.39	-0.14	0.05	-0.1	-0.21	-0.27	-0.24	0.14	-0.09	0.05	-0.16	0.0	-0.22	-0.39
C20:2n6	0.11	0.35	0.09	0.02	0.08	0.42	0.14	-0.04	0.46	0.0	0.03	0.76	0.33	0.18	0.08	0.13
C20:3n3	-0.07	-0.37	-0.51	-0.33	-0.3	-0.1	-0.03	-0.01	-0.33	0.01	-0.35	-0.32	-0.46	-0.29	-0.1	-0.46
C20:3n6	0.37	0.18	0.16	-0.19	-0.09	0.12	0.29	0.2	0.09	-0.2	-0.01	0.16	0.07	-0.09	0.23	0.02
C20:4n6	-0.01	0.14	0.37	-0.1	0.11	0.1	0.52	-0.08	0.24	-0.36	0.1	-0.32	0.06	-0.38	-0.49	0.28
C20:5n3	-0.14	0.08	0.14	-0.15	-0.07	-0.14	0.38	0.16	-0.12	-0.09	-0.03	-0.17	-0.3	0.11	0.04	0.15
C22:0	0.13	-0.24	-0.32	0.02	-0.2	-0.22	0.16	0.36	-0.37	-0.25	-0.53	-0.3	-0.39	0.07	0.33	-0.24
C22:1n9																
C22:2n6	0.1	-0.34	-0.42	-0.04	0.37	-0.19	-0.02	0.37	-0.33	0.03	-0.17	-0.02	-0.01	-0.35	0.15	-0.45

C22:6 n3	0.31	-0.31	-0.12	-0.43	-0.25	-0.43	0.25	0.43	-0.37	0.0	0.12	-0.43	-0.25	-0.43	0.31	-0.43
C23:0																
C24:0	0.05	-0.17	-0.48	-0.26	-0.34	-0.13	-0.08	-0.21	0.02	-0.06	-0.08	0.15	-0.1	0.07	-0.16	-0.39
C24:1	-0.51	-0.37	-0.45	-0.55	-0.37	-0.49	-0.33	-0.14	-0.56	0.27	0.38	-0.21	-0.44	-0.06	-0.14	-0.47
C8:0	-0.12	0.37	0.19	0.19	0.25	0.31	0.19	0.0	0.19	-0.37	0.0	0.37	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.31

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Table A5. Spearman correlation coefficients between individual fatty acids and auxins production.

Fatty Acid	A - not identified	A8 - Bacillus sanguinis	B4 - Exiguobacterium acetylicum	Bd - Exiguobacterium acetylicum	Bl - Exiguobacterium acetylicum	E - Peribacillus frigoriterans	F - Enterobacter quasihormaechei	Gw - Priestia aryabhattai	Gy - Peribacillus frigoriterans	H - Leclercia adecarbonylata	K - Enterobacter quasihormaechei	P - Priestia aryabhattai	Q - not identified	T - Bacillus australimaris	V - not identified	Z - Priestia megaterium
C10:0	-0.25	0.31	-0.43	-0.06	-0.43	0.43	0.43	-0.43	-0.19	-0.31	0.43	0.12	0.25	0.25	-0.19	0.31
C11:0	0.19	0.37	-0.37	0.25	0.31	0.31	0.12	0.06	-0.31	0.25	0.37	0.37	0.43	-0.31	0.06	0.19
C12:0	-0.11	-0.01	-0.51	-0.34	-0.59	0.3	0.08	-0.08	-0.1	-0.2	0.42	-0.2	0.02	0.09	-0.23	-0.01
C14:0	-0.02	-0.31	-0.18	-0.18	-0.32	-0.09	-0.34	0.29	0.2	0.05	0.14	-0.25	-0.25	0.19	-0.13	-0.05
C14:1	0.01	0.06	-0.05	0.11	-0.03	0.05	0.06	-0.13	0.26	-0.32	0.21	0.16	0.23	0.28	0.12	0.35
C15:0	0.32	-0.4	0.26	-0.09	-0.16	-0.02	-0.54	-0.12	0.48	0.01	0.03	-0.38	0.21	0.27	0.02	0.06
C16:0	-0.13	0.3	-0.13	-0.01	-0.1	0.25	0.21	0.23	-0.59	0.42	0.04	0.43	-0.2	-0.5	-0.12	0.09
C16:1	0.07	-0.32	-0.27	-0.03	0.05	0.06	-0.29	-0.21	0.32	-0.34	0.02	-0.28	0.14	0.49	0.09	-0.08
C17:0	0.35	0.07	0.35	-0.07	0.05	0.06	0.09	-0.29	0.2	-0.14	0.01	0.13	0.33	-0.0	0.17	0.28
C17:1	0.3	0.03	0.33	-0.08	-0.01	-0.17	0.04	-0.2	-0.0	0.26	0.17	0.1	-0.13	-0.35	-0.36	0.12
C18:0	0.0	-0.27	-0.02	0.31	0.15	-0.26	0.28	0.39	-0.37	0.28	0.08	0.18	-0.64	-0.38	-0.08	-0.22
C18:1 n9c+t	-0.11	-0.01	0.39	0.19	-0.01	-0.24	0.19	0.18	-0.04	-0.05	-0.29	0.28	-0.31	-0.01	0.04	0.29
C18:2 n6c	-0.03	0.38	0.42	-0.12	0.25	0.12	0.41	-0.3	0.04	-0.1	-0.18	0.27	0.23	-0.23	0.08	0.26
C18:2 n6t	-0.37	-0.25	-0.19	0.37	0.37	-0.43	0.25	0.43	0.0	-0.43	-0.43	-0.19	-0.37	0.37	0.37	-0.43
C18:3 n3	0.24	-0.12	0.62	0.03	0.29	-0.44	-0.2	-0.06	0.42	-0.23	-0.52	-0.22	0.13	0.16	0.23	-0.07
C18:3 n6	0.16	-0.05	0.14	0.1	-0.16	0.21	-0.42	0.01	-0.16	0.35	0.05	-0.05	0.25	-0.3	-0.03	-0.04
C20:0	0.12	0.1	0.52	0.11	0.12	-0.05	0.09	-0.26	-0.0	-0.04	-0.09	-0.02	0.19	-0.27	-0.28	0.19
C20:1	0.25	-0.08	0.48	0.04	-0.13	-0.19	-0.1	-0.24	0.04	-0.01	-0.15	0.06	-0.02	-0.12	-0.06	0.14
C20:2 n6	-0.13	0.41	0.27	0.03	-0.15	0.36	0.27	-0.56	-0.08	-0.2	0.03	0.11	0.48	0.03	-0.25	0.44
C20:3 n3	0.11	0.13	0.41	0.05	0.24	-0.27	-0.08	0.01	0.42	-0.03	-0.24	-0.21	0.37	0.23	0.42	-0.12
C20:3 n6	-0.3	0.06	-0.34	-0.47	-0.59	0.42	0.11	-0.21	-0.1	-0.21	0.16	-0.19	0.05	0.06	-0.1	-0.07
C20:4 n6	-0.5	0.23	-0.44	-0.51	-0.34	-0.07	0.3	0.08	0.0	-0.3	-0.03	-0.21	-0.25	0.13	-0.14	-0.23

C20:5 n3	-0.14	-0.13	-0.55	-0.34	-0.42	-0.06	-0.14	0.08	0.03	-0.09	0.28	-0.21	-0.28	0.13	-0.22	-0.21
C22:0	0.19	-0.66	0.15	0.36	0.25	-0.45	-0.31	0.38	0.35	-0.21	-0.21	-0.38	-0.22	0.43	0.35	-0.35
C22:2 n6	0.46	-0.27	0.51	0.41	-0.12	-0.2	-0.39	0.25	-0.21	0.44	-0.05	0.17	-0.18	-0.17	-0.14	0.18
C22:6 n3	0.12	-0.37	-0.25	-0.43	-0.37	-0.06	-0.37	0.37	0.06	0.06	0.12	-0.43	-0.25	-0.15	-0.12	-0.37
C24:0	0.14	0.06	0.76	-0.05	0.27	-0.04	0.0	-0.24	0.5	-0.2	-0.4	-0.05	0.34	0.26	0.24	0.3
C24:1	0.25	-0.12	-0.04	-0.23	0.16	0.19	-0.52	-0.15	0.26	0.2	-0.17	-0.19	0.28	0.2	0.17	-0.08
C8:0	-0.25	0.31	-0.43	-0.06	-0.43	0.43	0.43	-0.43	-0.19	-0.31	0.43	0.12	0.25	0.25	-0.19	0.31

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Table A6. Spearman correlation coefficients between individual fatty acids and ACC deaminase production.

Fatty Acid	A - not identified	A8 - Bacillus sanguinis	B4 - Exiguobacterium acetylicum	Bd - Exiguobacterium acetylicum	Bl - Exiguobacterium acetylicum	E - Peribacillus frigoriferans	F - Enterobacter quasihorquaechei	Gw - Priestia aryabhattai	Gy - Peribacillus frigoriferans	H - Leclercia adecarboxylata	K - Enterobacter quasihorquaechei	P - Priestia aryabhattai	Q - not identified	T - Bacillus australimaris	V - not identified	Z - Priestia megaterium
C10:0	-0.06	-0.06	0.06	0.25	0.43	-0.37	0.19	-0.19	-0.12	0.31	0.43	0.19	-0.12	0.06	0.12	-0.25
C11:0	0.43	0.0	0.0	0.19	0.12	-0.31	0.06	0.43	0.31	0.37	0.37	0.37	0.06	0.19	0.19	0.37
C12:0	-0.3	0.02	-0.25	-0.1	0.04	0.01	0.31	-0.36	-0.05	0.33	0.25	0.14	-0.22	-0.08	-0.09	-0.19
C14:0	-0.54	-0.04	-0.56	-0.4	-0.62	0.15	0.06	-0.52	-0.23	0.11	-0.2	-0.42	-0.32	0.17	-0.31	0.07
C14:1	-0.21	-0.02	-0.22	-0.2	0.2	-0.15	0.18	-0.4	-0.13	0.24	-0.03	0.12	-0.17	0.1	0.1	-0.1
C15:0	-0.35	0.36	-0.34	-0.12	-0.27	0.33	0.41	-0.1	-0.64	-0.04	-0.2	-0.13	-0.37	0.09	0.04	0.2
C16:0	0.34	-0.32	0.04	0.21	0.0	-0.09	-0.36	0.18	0.56	0.2	0.06	0.1	0.19	0.04	-0.11	0.23
C16:1	-0.3	0.08	-0.19	-0.01	-0.16	0.22	0.18	-0.2	-0.47	0.09	0.32	-0.27	-0.19	-0.05	0.15	-0.1
C17:0	0.16	0.28	0.28	0.18	0.6	-0.01	0.53	0.29	-0.17	-0.07	-0.06	0.46	0.17	-0.07	0.26	0.05
C17:1	0.3	0.56	-0.01	-0.04	0.23	0.09	0.28	0.36	-0.1	-0.31	-0.3	0.19	0.15	0.46	0.14	0.1
C18:0	0.15	0.23	0.02	-0.35	-0.18	-0.27	-0.26	-0.05	0.44	-0.13	-0.16	-0.17	0.29	0.39	-0.46	0.1
C18:1 n9c+t	-0.3	-0.23	-0.11	-0.12	0.04	-0.27	-0.11	-0.33	0.21	-0.27	-0.33	-0.15	0.46	0.15	-0.08	-0.09
C18:2 n6c	0.62	0.04	0.47	0.12	0.59	-0.06	0.15	0.42	0.17	-0.33	0.04	0.64	0.48	-0.18	0.4	0.04
C18:2 n6t	-0.43	-0.43	0.25	-0.25	-0.25	-0.43	-0.43	-0.43	0.37	-0.19	0.12	-0.43	0.37	-0.37	-0.37	-0.43
C18:3 n3	-0.15	0.08	0.27	0.05	0.25	0.15	0.18	0.15	-0.12	-0.43	-0.35	0.1	0.26	-0.37	0.19	-0.22
C18:3 n6	0.12	0.09	-0.2	0.16	-0.04	0.39	-0.18	0.12	0.04	0.35	-0.14	0.18	-0.48	-0.13	0.03	0.24
C20:0	0.34	0.33	0.09	-0.07	0.42	0.02	0.06	0.22	0.19	-0.33	-0.12	0.64	0.35	-0.18	0.35	-0.04
C20:1	-0.11	0.25	0.02	0.2	0.46	0.18	0.2	0.07	-0.11	-0.18	-0.35	0.1	0.11	0.09	0.18	-0.19
C20:2 n6	0.32	0.01	0.23	0.32	0.62	-0.13	0.01	0.16	0.01	-0.02	0.2	0.63	0.1	-0.3	0.46	-0.1
C20:3 n3	-0.01	0.01	0.5	0.16	0.11	-0.12	0.16	0.32	-0.29	-0.15	-0.32	0.01	-0.25	-0.24	-0.05	-0.02

C20:3 n6	-0.1	-0.17	-0.03	0.08	0.13	0.24	0.12	-0.27	-0.07	0.25	0.28	0.18	-0.24	-0.32	0.01	-0.22
C20:4 n6	-0.37	-0.41	-0.07	-0.12	-0.17	-0.09	0.1	-0.34	0.07	-0.21	0.14	-0.21	0.2	-0.06	-0.04	-0.49
C20:5 n3	-0.51	-0.06	-0.48	-0.2	-0.34	0.18	0.14	-0.46	-0.19	0.16	0.01	-0.44	-0.3	0.27	-0.16	-0.29
C22:0	-0.45	0.13	0.05	-0.42	-0.35	-0.04	-0.14	-0.38	-0.1	0.04	-0.25	-0.36	-0.23	-0.3	-0.51	-0.06
C22:2 n6	-0.13	0.16	-0.08	0.08	0.02	0.04	-0.32	-0.02	0.17	0.29	-0.58	-0.08	-0.27	-0.05	-0.38	0.26
C22:6 n3	-0.37	0.09	-0.43	-0.43	-0.43	0.43	0.25	-0.31	0.06	0.12	-0.12	0.0	-0.19	-0.19	-0.28	0.0
C24:0	0.24	0.06	0.44	0.04	0.29	0.03	0.19	0.25	-0.27	-0.39	-0.19	0.37	0.21	-0.42	0.25	0.15
C24:1	0.06	-0.01	0.01	0.43	-0.36	0.44	0.19	0.47	-0.59	-0.04	0.25	-0.34	-0.18	-0.0	0.24	0.38
C8:0	-0.06	-0.06	0.06	0.25	0.43	-0.37	0.19	-0.19	-0.12	0.31	0.43	0.19	-0.12	0.06	0.12	-0.25

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Table A7. Spearman correlation coefficients between individual fatty acids and siderophore production.

Fatty Acid	A - not identified	A8 - Bacillus sanguinis	B4 - Exiguobacterium acetylicum	Bd - Exiguobacterium acetylicum	Bl - Exiguobacterium acetylicum	E - Peribacterillus frigoriterans	F - Enterobacter quasiharmaechei	Gw - Priestia aryabhattai	Gy - Peribacterillus frigoriterans	H - Leclercia adecarboxylata	K - Enterobacter quasiharmaechei	P - Priestia aryabhattai	Q - not identified	T - Bacillus australimaris	V - not identified	Z - Priestia megaterium
C10:0	-0.31	-0.43	0.0	0.06	0.12	-0.37	0.43	-0.31	0.0	0.25	-0.12	0.06	0.06	0.12	0.0	0.06
C11:0	0.12	0.06	0.06	0.19	0.0	-0.25	0.06	0.37	-0.25	0.12	-0.37	0.0	0.19	0.31	0.31	0.19
C12:0	-0.5	-0.51	-0.21	-0.16	0.01	-0.33	0.13	-0.33	-0.08	0.02	-0.14	0.18	-0.16	0.01	-0.3	-0.21
C14:0	-0.36	0.26	-0.09	-0.02	0.16	-0.09	-0.1	-0.19	-0.14	-0.01	0.19	0.22	-0.16	0.13	-0.14	-0.23
C14:1	-0.19	0.05	-0.07	0.18	0.18	0.03	0.14	0.1	-0.03	0.06	0.38	0.05	-0.27	0.17	0.06	0.45
C15:0	-0.42	-0.19	-0.29	-0.16	-0.13	0.12	-0.33	-0.0	-0.15	-0.51	0.55	0.02	-0.32	-0.06	-0.42	0.05
C16:0	0.3	0.16	0.34	0.12	0.19	0.11	0.22	-0.1	0.07	0.3	-0.36	0.14	0.45	0.13	0.32	-0.1
C16:1	-0.35	-0.1	-0.41	-0.12	-0.18	-0.35	-0.3	0.21	-0.34	-0.25	0.05	-0.11	-0.25	0.02	-0.32	-0.07
C17:0	0.2	-0.44	0.06	0.09	-0.0	0.23	0.3	0.02	0.23	-0.1	0.29	0.03	0.09	-0.1	-0.03	0.2
C17:1	0.02	-0.05	-0.12	-0.26	-0.31	0.25	0.0	-0.36	-0.17	0.1	0.12	-0.42	-0.19	-0.45	-0.09	0.06
C18:0	0.02	0.4	0.04	0.01	-0.02	-0.08	0.03	-0.23	-0.26	0.45	-0.42	-0.24	0.12	-0.01	0.05	-0.1
C18:1 n9c+t	0.59	0.48	0.74	0.54	0.62	0.3	0.47	-0.05	0.62	0.56	0.24	0.52	0.55	0.29	0.65	-0.12
C18:2 n6c	0.38	-0.13	0.15	0.08	-0.12	0.51	0.22	0.2	0.23	-0.04	0.1	-0.16	-0.0	-0.13	0.18	0.46
C18:2 n6t	0.43	0.43	0.43	0.43	0.43	-0.43	0.19	0.31	0.43	0.43	-0.43	0.43	0.43	0.43	0.43	-0.43
C18:3 n3	0.56	-0.11	0.28	0.11	0.09	0.29	0.03	0.23	0.61	-0.17	0.39	0.22	0.11	-0.14	0.16	-0.13
C18:3 n6	-0.37	-0.32	-0.32	-0.35	-0.25	0.22	-0.57	0.08	-0.22	-0.58	0.25	-0.16	-0.35	-0.16	-0.4	0.32
C20:0	0.24	-0.21	0.13	-0.14	-0.14	0.35	-0.09	0.16	0.21	-0.13	0.22	-0.1	-0.24	-0.14	0.12	0.28
C20:1	0.2	-0.29	0.11	-0.07	-0.01	0.28	0.02	-0.22	0.32	0.02	0.38	-0.01	0.06	-0.35	-0.02	-0.01

C20:2 n6	0.1	-0.44	0.19	-0.02	0.03	0.2	0.2	0.05	0.28	-0.14	0.24	0.02	-0.07	0.03	0.14	0.37
C20:3 n3	0.16	-0.16	0.11	0.11	0.03	0.18	0.11	0.05	0.41	-0.33	0.33	0.07	0.04	-0.07	-0.03	0.11
C20:3 n6	-0.52	-0.61	-0.32	-0.28	-0.14	-0.04	-0.05	-0.25	-0.05	-0.25	-0.05	0.04	-0.25	-0.14	-0.47	0.01
C20:4 n6	0.06	0.06	0.2	0.1	0.17	-0.19	0.26	-0.23	0.37	0.4	-0.31	0.36	0.15	-0.03	0.21	-0.49
C20:5 n3	-0.46	0.01	-0.33	-0.2	-0.07	-0.34	-0.13	-0.36	-0.24	0.17	-0.12	-0.0	-0.24	-0.19	-0.25	-0.36
C22:0	-0.1	0.11	-0.11	0.03	0.13	-0.23	-0.13	0.13	-0.01	-0.2	0.13	0.08	-0.13	0.19	-0.25	-0.14
C22:2 n6	0.27	-0.02	0.34	0.01	0.35	0.15	0.18	-0.32	0.21	-0.01	0.36	0.17	0.27	0.06	0.09	-0.16
C22:6 n3	-0.37	-0.25	-0.31	-0.31	-0.12	-0.06	-0.31	-0.12	-0.12	-0.25	-0.06	0.19	-0.31	-0.12	-0.43	-0.37
C24:0	0.39	-0.08	0.26	0.18	0.1	0.56	0.25	0.27	0.42	-0.37	0.56	0.1	0.02	0.08	0.1	0.35
C24:1	-0.03	-0.03	-0.22	-0.1	-0.25	-0.06	-0.31	0.25	-0.26	-0.49	0.03	-0.06	0.17	-0.03	-0.24	-0.25
C8:0	-0.31	-0.43	0.0	0.06	0.12	-0.37	0.43	-0.31	0.0	0.25	-0.12	0.06	0.06	0.12	0.0	0.06

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Table A8. Spearman correlation coefficients between individual fatty acids and proline production.

Fatty Acid	A - not identified	A8 - Bacillus sanguinis	B4 - Exiguobacterium acetylicum	Bd - Exiguobacterium acetylicum	Bl - Exiguobacterium acetylicum	E - Peribacillus frigoriterans	F - Enterobacter quasihorquaechei	Gw - Priestia aryabhattai	Gy - Peribacillus frigoriterans	H - Leclercia adecarboxylata	K - Enterobacter quasihorquaechei	P - Priestia aryabhattai	Q - not identified	T - Bacillus australimaris	V - not identified	Z - Priestia megaterium
C10:0	0.12	0.19	-0.43	-0.43	-0.31	-0.43	-0.43	-0.31	-0.43	-0.43	-0.18	-0.12	-0.31	-0.06	0.06	-0.43
C11:0	0.31	0.37	0.43	0.25	0.25	0.06	0.06	-0.43	0.31	0.12	0.25	0.19	0.06	0.25	0.37	0.12
C12:0	-0.03	0.02	-0.59	-0.42	-0.5	-0.55	-0.55	-0.37	-0.55	-0.51	-0.18	-0.22	-0.24	0.04	-0.21	-0.59
C14:0	-0.12	0.17	-0.03	0.33	0.18	-0.04	-0.23	0.28	-0.02	-0.02	0.34	0.3	0.03	0.24	-0.15	0.18
C14:1	0.12	0.58	0.21	0.21	0.19	0.1	-0.17	-0.02	0.18	-0.1	0.45	0.3	-0.22	0.23	-0.04	0.13
C15:0	0.04	-0.14	0.02	0.26	0.11	-0.09	-0.37	0.08	-0.01	-0.01	0.52	0.18	-0.15	-0.04	-0.24	0.1
C16:0	-0.01	0.1	-0.11	-0.14	-0.21	0.01	0.23	-0.15	-0.15	-0.15	-0.6	-0.46	0.12	-0.09	-0.02	-0.21
C16:1	-0.06	0.12	0.06	0.08	0.03	0.01	-0.53	-0.02	0.12	0.25	0.58	0.36	0.15	-0.09	-0.02	0.12
C17:0	0.36	-0.26	-0.31	-0.34	-0.36	-0.39	0.02	-0.35	-0.28	-0.33	-0.22	-0.4	-0.4	-0.13	-0.08	-0.41
C17:1	-0.16	-0.28	-0.23	-0.19	0.01	-0.39	0.39	-0.08	-0.22	-0.16	-0.14	-0.2	-0.37	-0.24	-0.15	-0.05
C18:0	-0.42	-0.1	0.1	0.09	0.14	0.16	0.7	0.35	0.36	0.29	-0.19	0.19	0.48	-0.1	0.29	0.31
C18:1 n9c+t	0.4	0.09	-0.07	0.0	0.02	-0.06	0.14	0.26	-0.1	-0.3	-0.25	-0.22	-0.36	-0.15	-0.16	0.25
C18:2 n6c	0.04	0.05	0.03	-0.24	-0.15	0.04	0.34	-0.04	0.02	-0.09	-0.35	-0.3	-0.21	0.02	-0.03	-0.16
C18:2 n6t	0.19	-0.06	0.25	0.12	0.19	0.37	0.12	0.43	0.43	0.37	0.0	0.43	0.43	0.19	0.43	0.43
C18:3 n3	0.47	-0.47	-0.08	-0.14	-0.06	-0.11	0.04	-0.05	-0.11	-0.13	-0.16	-0.24	-0.42	-0.1	-0.19	-0.03
C18:3 n6	-0.15	0.06	0.19	0.14	-0.04	0.27	-0.21	-0.3	0.04	-0.06	0.02	-0.22	0.06	-0.18	-0.34	-0.15
C20:0	0.18	0.04	0.03	-0.18	0.08	-0.13	0.06	-0.2	0.02	-0.28	-0.13	-0.21	-0.57	-0.09	-0.37	-0.05

C20:1	0.22	-0.41	-0.42	-0.45	-0.38	-0.39	-0.08	-0.33	-0.5	-0.48	-0.38	-0.62	-0.56	-0.6	-0.44	-0.27
C20:2 n6	0.3	0.22	-0.14	-0.32	-0.08	-0.18	-0.28	-0.3	-0.22	-0.43	-0.15	-0.31	-0.6	-0.06	-0.28	-0.34
C20:3 n3	0.25	-0.49	0.19	0.21	0.2	0.19	0.31	0.19	0.1	0.16	0.06	0.14	0.02	0.33	0.37	0.04
C20:3 n6	-0.29	-0.02	-0.56	-0.52	-0.68	-0.25	-0.55	-0.26	-0.55	-0.41	-0.4	-0.44	-0.03	-0.12	-0.32	-0.69
C20:4 n6	0.01	-0.12	-0.46	-0.39	-0.35	-0.37	-0.31	0.06	-0.57	-0.35	-0.37	-0.17	-0.24	0.11	-0.04	-0.18
C20:5 n3	-0.26	0.02	-0.34	-0.14	-0.2	-0.32	-0.4	-0.08	-0.41	-0.19	0.09	0.05	-0.06	-0.06	-0.16	-0.1
C22:0	-0.04	-0.17	0.26	0.42	0.34	0.37	0.22	0.43	0.57	0.47	0.39	0.58	0.49	0.29	0.25	0.28
C22:2 n6	0.31	-0.23	-0.2	0.09	0.1	-0.12	0.32	-0.13	-0.08	-0.23	-0.28	-0.35	-0.2	-0.14	-0.26	-0.24
C22:6 n3	-0.19	-0.19	-0.37	-0.12	-0.37	-0.31	-0.31	-0.19	-0.31	-0.25	-0.19	-0.19	0.0	0.12	-0.37	-0.37
C24:0	0.29	-0.08	0.12	0.12	0.16	0.15	0.23	0.3	0.2	0.06	0.04	-0.0	-0.21	0.27	-0.03	-0.01
C24:1	0.07	-0.32	0.08	0.18	0.0	0.01	-0.32	-0.01	-0.03	0.38	0.33	0.03	0.29	-0.15	0.08	0.07
C8:0	0.12	0.19	-0.43	-0.43	-0.31	-0.43	-0.43	-0.31	-0.43	-0.43	-0.06	-0.12	-0.31	-0.06	0.06	-0.43

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